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Main Author(s):	CSTB – BRACHET Aline		
Contributor(s):	CSTB – PASTORELLY Nicolas, PIGEON Pierre, QUENARD Mathieu, SCHIOPU Nicoleta RINA-C – MARASI Alberto, PEREZ AGUIRRE ECHEVARRIA Pedro		
Reviewed by:	HSLU (DMITRIEVA Jekaterina), SAK (STEMPLINGER Florian)		
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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ADD	Agenzia del Demanio
API	Application Programming Interface
BAFh	Harmonised Biotype Area Factor
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BMS	Building Management Systems
CAIDI	Customer Average Interruption Duration Index
CAIFI	Customer Average Interruption Frequency Index
CCI	Cooling Comfort Index
CP	Charging Points
CTAIDI	Customer Total Average Interruption Duration Index
EE	Electric Energy
ESC-B	Electricity self-consumption at Building Level
ESS-B	Electricity self-sufficiency at Building Level
EV	Electric Vehicles
FWEP	Freshwater Eutrophication
GIS	Geographic Information System
GWFE	Global Warning for Freshwater Ecosystem
GWP	Global Warming Potential
GWTE	Global Warning for Terrestrial Ecosystem
HCI	Heating Comfort Index
HVAC	Heating, Cooling & Air Conditioning
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
INN	Innovation
IoT	Internet of Things
KF	Key-Functionalities
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LCA	Life-cycle assessment
N/A	Not Applicable
P2P	Peer2Peer
PCR	Product Category Rules
PDH	Personalised Building Data Hubs
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RUL	Remaining Useful Life
SAIDI	System Average Interruption Duration Index Reduction
SAIFI	System Average Interruption Frequency Index
SRES-B	Share of Renewable at Building Level
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TA	Terrestrial Acidification
UCs	Use Cases
WCAE	Water consumption for aquatic ecosystems
WCTE	Water consumption for Terrestrial ecosystem

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable represents the first report of the WILSON project on the development of a methodology to assess urban planning projects from both biodiversity and climate perspectives.

The report provides an overview of existing LCA practices at product, building and district scales across 14 European countries, highlighting differences in methodological approaches and levels of regulatory integration. This comparative analysis helps identify gaps, opportunities for standardisation and key levers to support future harmonisation at the European level. The benchmarking exercise shows that 6 out of 14 countries have already embedded LCA into their building regulations, demonstrating a growing but uneven integration across Europe. It also highlights the importance of national databases and regulatory frameworks in facilitating data access, improving consistency, and balancing the effort of data collection with the robustness of results. Overall, the review reveals two structural gaps in current practices: uneven regulatory integration across countries and the limited consideration of biodiversity-related indicators, which restricts the capacity of conventional LCA to capture ecological impacts and benefits.

Against this backdrop, the deliverable identifies two key challenges for advancing assessment frameworks in urban projects: ensuring the availability and quality of input data beyond energy uses, and developing robust, multi-scale methodologies capable of integrating both carbon and biodiversity dimensions. While carbon indicators are widely implemented, biodiversity remains insufficiently addressed despite its central role in achieving climate and ecological transitions.

Building on this context, the deliverable introduces the HIBOU approach (Innovation 6 of the WILSON project (INN 6)), a quantitative framework designed to assess carbon, biodiversity impacts and Urban Heat Island (UHI) in a harmonised way. By combining carbon indicators with biodiversity-related pressures and ecosystem-based metrics (including in-situ and ex-situ dimensions), HIBOU responds to a major gap in conventional LCA, which traditionally overlooks ecological benefits and biodiversity support. It provides a harmonised toolset to support urban stakeholders in making informed decisions and reducing greenwashing risks. The report presents conceptual foundations of HIBOU, the indicators it produces, and the input/output data required (in connection with Material Passports development).

More specifically, within the WILSON project, HIBOU has been operationalised through the consolidation of eight indicators covering both climate change and biodiversity-related pressures:

- Global Warming Potential (GWP, kg CO₂eq/m²);
- Global Warming for Terrestrial Ecosystems (GWTE, PDF·m²·year);
- Global Warming for Freshwater Ecosystems (GWFE, PDF·m²·year);
- Terrestrial Acidification (TA, PDF·m²·year);
- Freshwater Eutrophication (FWE, PDF·m²·year);
- Water Consumption for Terrestrial Ecosystems (WCTE, PDF·m²·year);
- Water Consumption for Aquatic Ecosystems (WCAE, PDF·m²·year);

- and the Harmonised Biotope Area Factor (BAFh), which captures in-situ biodiversity support.

Together, these indicators provide an integrated perspective combining carbon emissions, biodiversity pressures, and ecological functionality at multiple scales.

Finally, the report provides recommendations to support harmonisation of LCA practices in line with evolving European regulations, drawing lessons from the HIBOU approach to guide future methodological improvements. In particular, it highlights the need to strengthen methodological consistency across scales (product, building, district), improve interoperability of data systems, and progressively integrate biodiversity-related metrics into regulatory and voluntary assessment frameworks.

Looking forward, the report outlines the next steps for testing and validating HIBOU in pilot cases at the European scale. These pilot applications, particularly the Italian pilot site to be documented in a second version of this deliverable (due in October 2026), will allow for methodological consolidation and operational validation of the framework. These experiments will be critical to demonstrate the added value of integrating carbon and biodiversity assessments into planning and regulatory frameworks.

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1. Scope of the deliverable

This document constitutes the first deliverable of the WILSON project report on the biodiversity and climate KPI calculation method.

It focuses on the methodological aspects of the HIBOU approach (Innovation 6 (INN 6)), including the conceptual framework and the development of indicators to assess urban planning projects from a climate change and biodiversity perspectives.

For the biodiversity KPIs, both in situ (local) and ex - situ (global) impacts will be assessed. The nexus between the two types of impacts will be considered through the end point Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach. A second deliverable will be dedicated to the application of the method to a real-world case study: the Italian pilot site.

2.2. Structure of the deliverable

Section 1 of this deliverable, provides the “Executive Summary” and Section 2, provides the “Introduction”.

Section 3 of this deliverable presents a state-of-the-art review of how LCA methodologies are currently implemented at the product, building and district scales across European countries. The objective is to identify existing national practices, understand their level of advancement, and assess whether it is possible to harmonise different approaches or select one as a reference for further development. This comparative analysis will serve as a foundation for establishing a robust methodological framework.

Section 4 of the deliverable is dedicated to the presentation of the HIBOU method. It provides a detailed overview of the conceptual framework of the method, its objectives, and its operational structure. This section describes the indicators produced by the method, the principles and models used for their calculation, and the nature and format of input and output data required. It also discusses the current limitations of the approach, as well as potential perspectives for the results discussion and for the future developments.

Section 5 of this deliverable provides recommendations to support the harmonisation of LCA practices at the European level, based on the future European standard (e.g., Construction Products Regulation (CPR) and Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)) and the lessons learned from the HIBOU method. It also discusses the main limitations of the HIBOU approach in terms environmental assessing tool. These reflections aim to inform future methodological developments and support the implementation of more robust and operational environmental assessments for Europe.

Sections 6 and 7 presents respectively the main outcomes and the author’s conclusions, and the reference used for the elaboration of the document.

2.3. Relation with other tasks and deliverables

The work performed in the context of “Buildings impacts linked to the climate change & biodiversity nexus” is closely interconnected with several other activities of the WILSON project (cf. Figure 1):

- Link with “Baseline assessment and performance indicators of buildings and portfolios”: it defines the reference set of KPIs used across the WILSON project. The HIBOU method is designed to produce a subset of these KPIs, specifically those related to carbon and biodiversity performance at the building and district scales.
- Link with “Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy uses (I)”: the developments carried out in this framework will deliver the inputs data required to compute the HIBOU KPIs.
- Link with “Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for non-energy uses (I)”:
 - Firstly, “CIMBA: predictive maintenance” addresses the development of a predictive maintenance tool, which could have an impact on the inputs and outputs of the HIBOU method.
 - Then, the activities related to “Buildings risk assessment, vulnerability and resilience to climate change” will contribute to enriching the integrated assessment framework of HIBOU method by feeding it with complementary indicators on UHI.
 - Finally, the work concerning “LCA/LCC: environmental & social assessment on BMS” may also influence the results of the HIBOU method, especially regarding dynamic data inputs.

Figure 1: Relations of task 11.2/12.2 with other tasks

3. STATE OF THE ART: LCA PRACTICES IN EUROPE

LCA is an essential and increasingly recognised tool for evaluating the environmental impacts of buildings, products, or construction solutions across their entire life cycle (from the extraction of raw materials to end-of-life). Its methodological principles and requirements are defined by international standards, notably ISO 14040 [1] and ISO 14044 [2]. Highly adaptable, LCA can be applied at various scales, from individual products to entire urban districts, and is relevant to a wide range of stakeholders, including designers, manufacturers, and public authorities. It can be used at all stages of the building process, from design and production to construction, maintenance, and decommissioning.

For the construction sector, European standards have been developed to propose a framework to harmonise the environmental assessments and to ensure their comparability and their reliability:

- The EN 15804 standard [3] establishes the rules to create Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) for construction products;
- The EN 15978 standard [4] governs the assessment of the overall environmental performance of buildings, including construction, use, and end-of-life phases.

Moreover, the European Commission has introduced two frameworks to harmonise LCA methodologies improving consistency of assessments within the European Union: the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) for the product scale and Level(s) for the building scale. Both frameworks provide a common language to assess and report on the sustainability performance of products or buildings. They offer an integrated approach focused on LCA to encourage the consideration of environmental impacts throughout the life cycle [5], [6]. It should be noted that there is currently no harmonised European framework to conduct LCA at the district scale.

In this standardisation context, databases play a crucial role by providing reliable and representative impact factors. The Swiss-origin Ecoinvent database is widely used across Europe and contains over 20000 reliable life-cycle inventory datasets, covering around 3500 distinct products across all economic sectors (e.g., industrial processes, materials, etc.) [7].

Within these perspectives, it is interesting to examine how this global European framework (ISO and EN standards, PEF, Level(s), etc.) is concretely implemented at the national level. This part provides a review of 14 European countries LCA practices in the construction and planning sector. It examines methodologies, data and tool implemented at three complementary scales:

- Construction products (via EPDs)
- Buildings (particularly through emerging carbon regulations)
- District (from a systemic urban perspective).

3.1. WILSON consortium's countries

3.1.1. Spain

In Spain, LCA is increasingly used as a decision-making tool in the construction sector, especially to evaluate the environmental performance of buildings and infrastructure. While LCA is not yet mandatory at a national regulatory level, it is strongly promoted through various voluntary schemes, certification systems, and European alignment efforts. Its application is growing in both public and private projects, at multiple scales (from the individual product to the district level).

At the construction product scale, Spain follows the European standards EN 15804 and ISO 14040/14044 for the development of EPDs (e.g. Ata-Ali et al., 2021; Fraile-Garcia et al., 2015). The country does not yet have a centralised national environmental database, however several initiatives exist, such as:

- The [BEDEC database](#), developed by the Catalan Institute of Construction Technology¹ (ITeC), provides environmental information (Ecoinvent-based) for materials and construction products commonly used in Spain [10];
- EPD Spain (Environdec) is the main operator for EPDs in Spain and is part of the [ECO Platform](#)². This platform authorises EPDs compliant with EN 15804. This database contains 38 Spanish EPDs [11];
- [DAPcons](#) (Declaración Ambiental de Producto de Construcción) is an EPD programme, launched in 2008 by the Col·legi d'Aparelladors de Barcelona³ (CATEB) [12] with support from the Generalitat de Catalunya⁴. It's fully compliant with UNE-EN 15804, and is certified by the ECO Platform, ensuring that DAPcons EPDs carry the ECO Platform verified label. This database contains 137 Spanish EPDs [13].

At the building scale, LCA application is often linked to voluntary green building certification schemes, such as:

- BREEAM España (Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method) [14];
- LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design) [15], [16] and
- Spanish VERDE certification system [17], which encourage the inclusion of life-cycle thinking in design and construction.

¹ The Catalan Institute of Construction Technology (ITeC) is a non-profit foundation based in Barcelona that provides technical support and innovation for the construction sector.

² EcoPlatform is a European association that promotes the harmonisation and mutual recognition of EPDs based on EN 15804. It brings together EPD program operators and stakeholders to ensure high-quality, comparable LCA data for construction products across Europe.

³ The Col·legi d'Aparelladors de Barcelona (CATEB) is the official association of technical architects and building engineers in Barcelona, supporting over 8,000 professionals. It promotes high-quality, sustainable construction through training, certification, and initiatives such as the DAPcons.

⁴ The Generalitat de Catalunya is the autonomous government of Catalonia, responsible for regional administration, including areas such as environment, urban planning, and infrastructure. It plays a key role in promoting sustainable development and circular economy strategies within the region.

The Spanish Green Building Council⁵ (GBCe) [18] plays a central role in promoting the use of LCA via the VERDE certification system, which includes environmental performance indicators aligned with EN 15978 and Level(s). The VERDE methodology covers life-cycle stages A1–A5 (product and construction), B6 (energy use), C1–C4 (end-of-life), and optionally module D. The standard reference service life is 50 years. It also encourages the use of LCA and Life Cycle Cost (LCC) across the building life cycle (from early design to demolition) and awards points for reductions in carbon footprint and other impact categories[17].

At the district scale, LCA application is still emerging. Some pilot projects have been launched, notably under EU programs such as LIFE or Horizon Europe, and within regional planning agencies such as the Horizon 2020 project “URBANEW” [19]. These initiatives combine LCA with other sustainability indicators (such as energy mix, mobility infrastructure, and green-blue networks) to support the planning of low-carbon, resilient urban areas. However, there is currently no harmonised methodology or regulatory requirement for LCA at this scale in Spain.

On the policy side, LCA is incorporated indirectly into public procurement and urban planning through instruments like Spain’s Climate Change and Energy Transition Law (2021) [20] or the National Circular Economy Strategy (España Circular 2030) [21]. Although no mandatory national LCA thresholds are currently required, LCA is increasingly included in public tenders as a differentiating criterion for sustainable construction projects, especially when European funding is involved.

In terms of tools and software, professionals mainly use international LCA platforms such as SimaPro [22], One Click LCA [23], and OpenLCA [24], occasionally integrated with BIM systems for early-stage impact analysis. GBCe has also developed its own tools (VERDE Building 2022 [25]) to facilitate LCA-based performance assessment within the VERDE certification framework. However, accessibility, training, and data availability remain barriers to widespread adoption, particularly among small and medium-sized design offices.

Finally, Spain is also involved in several European efforts for harmonisation, including the adoption of Level(s) indicators in pilot projects and the testing of the PEF methodologies in selected sectors.

3.1.2. France

In France, LCA has become a central tool in the environmental regulation of the construction sector, particularly since its regulatory integration through the RE2020⁶, which came into force in January 2022. This environmental regulation for new buildings imposes carbon

⁵ The Spanish Green Building Council (GBCe) is a non-profit organisation dedicated to promoting sustainable building practices and green construction in Spain. It supports the implementation of environmental certifications and LCA methodologies to improve the environmental performance of buildings.

⁶ RE2020 is the French environmental regulation setting energy and carbon performance requirements for new buildings. It notably integrates dynamic LCA to evaluate and reduce greenhouse gas emissions over the entire building life cycle.

thresholds (expressed in $\text{kgCO}_2\text{e}/\text{m}^2/\text{year}$) that must be met over the life cycle of residential and office buildings [26]. LCA in France is therefore not only a voluntary tool, but a regulatory obligation, making the country a pioneer in Europe in this domain.

At the construction product scale, the French approach is grounded in a national methodological framework and relies on the [INIES database](#), the French national database of Environmental and Health Declaration Sheets (FDES), which are EPDs enriched with health information, and other EPDs in the construction sector, compliant with EN 15804 and ISO 14040/14044 standards. Additionally, the [PEP ecopassport](#) program, also based in France, is a member of [ECO Platform](#). This program focuses on the environmental assessment of electrical and electronic products and is recognised for its compliance with EcoPlatform standards [27]. INIES is containing 4928 FDES et 1596 Profils Environnementaux de Produit (PEP) [28]. Softwares as Simapro[22], OpenLCA [24] or Brightway [29] are used to model this kind of data.

At the building scale, The LCA methodology is based on EN 15978 and includes life-cycle stages A1–A5 (product and construction), B1–B7 (use phase including maintenance, energy, and water use), C1–C4 (end-of-life), and module D (benefits and loads beyond the system boundary). The standard reference study period is set at 50 years. The carbon performance indicator is expressed in $\text{kgCO}_2\text{e}/\text{m}^2$ over the full life cycle, and maximum thresholds apply depending on building type and year [30].

LCA in France is performed at the building scale using dedicated tools, for example ElodiebyCype [31], U2IWin [32], Nooco [33], or Pleiades [34], all of which are compliant with RE2020 rules (and so with ISO 14040/14044 and EN 15978). These software tools are relatively easy to use because they are connected to national EPD databases at the construction product scale (e.g., INIES), which provide the environmental impacts of materials and equipment for a given functional unit. Moreover, the French observatory OPEE (Observatoire de la Performance Énergétique et Environnementale), coordinated by the CSTB, is monitoring and analysing how LCA are applied in building projects across the country [35]. It was established to support the national transition toward low-carbon construction, especially in the context of the RE2020 regulation, and to provide feedback on practices, tools, and data used by stakeholders. OPEE collects and synthesises data from real LCA applications on buildings to evaluate the implementation of methods, identify areas of improvement, and contribute to the continuous enhancement of environmental regulations and LCA methodologies in France. It also plays a role in promoting transparency and consistency across LCA practices.

Beyond the building scale, several research and initiatives are emerging to apply LCA to the district scale, although no harmonised European reference framework yet exists. Initiatives such as the “Quartier Énergie Carbone” method promoted by ADEME⁷ [36] and the UrbanPrint software, co-developed by Efficacity and CSTB [37], aim to extend the RE2020

⁷ The ADEME (French Environment and Energy Management Agency) is a public agency under the joint authority of the French Ministries for Ecological Transition and Research. It supports the implementation of public policies in the areas of environment, energy, and sustainable development by funding research, providing expertise, and promoting best practices, including in the construction and building sectors.

logic to larger urban systems by integrating impacts related to infrastructure, mobility, outdoor space, etc.

It is important to note that in the French system, FDES (which provide life-cycle data at the construction product level) are calculated using a static LCA approach, meaning they do not account for the timing of emissions over the life cycle. However, this limitation is compensated at the building level through the methodology defined by the RE2020. When calculating the building's overall carbon impact, a dynamic LCA approach is applied: a time-dependent weighting factor is used to modulate the impact of greenhouse gas emissions according to the moment they occur over the building's life cycle [38], [39]. Emissions that happen earlier in the timeline are weighted more heavily than those occurring later (e.g., at demolition), reflecting their higher contribution to near-term global warming. This makes France one of the only countries in Europe to operationalise a time-weighted LCA at a regulatory level.

France also participates in European efforts for methodological harmonisation, notably through the Level(s) framework and contributes to initiatives around the PEF. These frameworks aim to ensure interoperability and common principles for sustainability assessments across Europe.

3.1.3. Netherland

In the Netherlands, LCA has been integrated into building regulations for over a decade, making the country one of the European pioneers in applying LCA systematically at the building level. Since 2013, the Dutch Building Decree (Bouwbesluit⁸) requires that all new residential and office buildings (over 100m²) submit a quantified environmental performance assessment based on LCA. This requirement is operationalised through an indicator call the "Environmental Performance of Buildings" (Milieuprestatie Gebouwen⁹ (MPG)), which assigns a monetised environmental impact score to each building, expressed in euros per square meter per year [40].

At the construction product scale, the Nationale Milieudatabase (NMD) is the Dutch national environmental data repository [41]. It includes both generic profiles and verified EPDs, all compliant with EN 15804. Manufacturers are encouraged to submit EPDs for their products which are third-party verified and published in the NMD. As of July 2025, the database contains over 4900 product profiles, covering a wide spectrum of construction categories [42]. Also, the Dutch EDP operator MRPI (Milieu Relevante Product Informatie) provides independently verified EPD certificates and is a recognised program operator linked to the EcoPlatform [43]. EPDs are created using standard LCA software such as SimaPro, Gabi, or openLCA.

⁸ National regulation that sets mandatory technical requirements for buildings in the Netherlands, including safety, health, usability, energy efficiency, and environmental performance. It applies to both new constructions and existing buildings undergoing renovation, ensuring compliance with national and European standards.

⁹ Dutch regulatory method that quantifies the environmental impact of new residential and office buildings based on LCA.

At the building scale, the LCA methodology is based on the mandatory indicator MPG, which expresses the environmental cost in euros per square meter per year over a reference study period of 75 years. The methodology is aligned on EN 15978 and follows national guidelines set out in the “Bepalingsmethode Milieuprestatie Bouwwerken”¹⁰ [44]: modules A1–A5 (product and construction), B1–B5 (use phase excluding energy and water), C1–C4 (end-of-life), and D (benefits beyond the system boundary). Operational energy is excluded from the MPG but addressed separately via energy performance regulation (BENG¹¹) [45]. The environmental performance is calculated based on life-cycle data from the NMD, using standard quantity take-offs from construction works. At the building design phase, as in France, the NMD lists validated calculation tools for MPG compliance [46], including several LCA software tools such as: BIMPACT [47], MRPI MPG Master [48], or the GPR software [49]. The tools are designed to be user-friendly for practitioners and are used by architects, engineers, and sustainability consultants.

At the policy level, the Dutch approach is distinctive in using monetary valuation of environmental impacts. Indeed, the MPG set a score by aggregating the environmental impacts of construction materials over the life cycle using shadow prices (the monetised cost of each environmental impact category: climate change, resource depletion, toxicity, etc.). The score is capped at a regulatory threshold that has been progressively tightened over time: they now stand at 0.8 €/m²/year for new residential building and 1.0 for office building [50].

Beyond the building scale, Dutch actors are investing in urban-scale LCA, particularly through initiatives such as the Amsterdam’s circular building programme [51] or the City Deal Circulaire Stad which include aspects on the urban environmental footprint and on the modelling of material flows in development projects [52].

3.1.4. Italy

In Italy, the application of LCA in the construction sector is facing a constant evolution, combining European regulations, national strategies and voluntary market initiatives. While the country aligns with construction EU standards (EN 15804, EN 15978) and international frameworks (ISO 14040/44), specific national instruments, such as the the “Criteri Ambientali Minimi”¹² (CAM) and the Italian LCA Database (BDI-LCA), play a key role in adapting methodologies to local conditions. Alongside product-level EPD schemes, voluntary certification systems, and EU-funded urban-scale pilot projects, Italy’s practice demonstrates both progress and fragmentation.

¹⁰ Official Dutch calculation guideline that defines how to perform LCA for buildings and civil engineering works in the Netherlands.

¹¹ Bijna Energieneutrale Gebouwen or Nearly Zero Energy Buildings refers to the Dutch energy performance regulation for new buildings, effective since 2021. It sets minimum requirements for energy efficiency, renewable energy use, and total energy demand, and complements the MPG by covering the operational energy aspects of buildings.

¹² Criteri Minimi Ambientali means Minimum Environmental Criteria. These criteria were established by the Italian government to promote sustainability in public procurement and to drive public procurement towards low-impact solutions, as part of the Green Public Procurement (GPP) strategy.

At the construction product level, Italy adopts the European standards EN 15804 and ISO 14040/14044 as the basis for developing EPDs. To ensure reliability and accuracy of LCA studies, an Italian online public LCA Database (BDI-LCA¹³), developed within the ARCADIA project coordinated by ENEA, is now available. Designed to become the national reference for the construction sector, this database is fully aligned with ISO 14040 and 14044. Moreover, the EPD Italy program¹⁴, compliant with EN 15804, plays a key role by ensuring product-level data compatibility with the Eco Platform, fostering harmonisation across Europe.

At the building scale, LCA application is often linked to voluntary green building certification schemes, such as LEED and BREEAM, which encourage the incorporation of life-cycle thinking in design and construction processes. It is therefore significant to note that, in 2024, Italy ranked eighth in the USGBC’s global ranking for number of LEED-certified buildings, being the only European country in the top ten, with 174 certified projects and more than 2.1 million square meters of surface area [53].

Regarding the urban scale, Italy has not yet established regulatory obligations or a standardised methodology for applying LCA. Nevertheless, in recent years an emerging trend has been observed, with various research teams and pilot projects evaluating both embodied and operational impacts at neighbourhood and district levels. These studies are mostly based on voluntary standards and European-funded projects rather than national regulations. Among them, some studies demonstrate that urban-scale LCA is technically feasible by combining data-driven engines, regional open-source datasets, and LCI libraries to produce comparative district scenarios [54], [55]. However, most studies emphasise the need to harmonise fundamental aspects, such as functional units and the management of information gaps [56], highlighting the considerable work still required in this field

At a policy level, the LCA is well integrated into environmental policies and public procurement. For example:

- Through the “Criteri Ambientali Minimi” (CAM), or Minimum Environmental Criteria, the Italian government has promoted sustainability in public procurement by encouraging the adoption of low-impact solutions, as part of the Green Public Procurement (GPP) strategy. The CAMs recommend using LCAs and LCCs to evaluate the environmental and financial value of projects such as the demolition or refurbishment of existing buildings. The adoption of these tools is rewarded in public tenders, as it allows to optimise design solutions, demonstrate environmental improvements compared to the base project and support the choice of improvement variants [57];
- Within the framework of the Next Generation EU Programme, the PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan) funds large-scale renovation projects, from individual buildings to entire urban districts, promoting energy efficiency. This program is guided by the DNSH (Do No Significant Harm) principle.

¹³ <https://bancadatiitalianalca.enea.it/Node/>

¹⁴ <https://www.epditaly.it/>

Although the LCA methodology is based on EN 15978 and EN 15804, the scope and depth of implementation can vary depending on project type and funding source. The typical reference study period is 50 years, and life-cycle stages A1–A3 are systematically required, with recommendations for including stages A4–C4 and D where data is available.

In term of tools and software, despite progress in creating the Italian-specific LCA database, professionals mainly use internationally recognised LCA platforms, such as LCA for Experts (GaBi), OpenLCA and SimaPro. Despite being generic and not meeting the specific needs of designers, these software programmes guarantee analyses aligned with current standards and the use of international databases such as GaBi and Ecoinvent. Significant international developments are underway to integrate BIM systems with LCA analysis tools, with the aim of making it possible to assess environmental impacts at an early design stage. However, in Italy the adoption of these integrated solutions is still limited.

Finally, it is relevant to note that in May 2025, GBC Italia launched a survey to assess the level of uptake and competence in the use of LCA in the construction sector. The survey, addressed to public administration and professionals in the building industry sector, aims to collect useful data to identify priority areas for action, both in terms of policy and training. The results, currently under development, will be integrated into the "Italian Roadmap to Achieve the 2050 Climate Goals", helping to outline concrete strategies for the ecological transition of the construction sector [58].

3.1.5. Greece

In Greece, LCA is progressively gaining attention as an essential tool to address environmental challenges in the construction sector. The need to reduce carbon emissions and enhance sustainability in buildings is driving interest in LCA both at product and building scales.

Currently, there is no binding national regulation mandating the use of LCA for construction projects in Greece. However, efforts to align with European climate targets, such as those embedded in the European Green Deal¹⁵ and the Fit for 55 package¹⁶, are encouraging the gradual integration of life-cycle thinking in the Greek construction industry. In this context, Greece has taken part in EU-funded initiatives such as the LIFE SUSCON project, which aims to promote sustainable construction practices through the application of LCA and environmental performance evaluation. This project reflects the country's growing engagement in aligning its construction sector with European sustainability objectives [59]. The Greek Ministry of Environment and Energy, in collaboration with academic institutions and industry stakeholders, supports initiatives to raise awareness and build capacity on LCA methodologies [60].

¹⁵ The European Green Deal is the European Union's strategic roadmap aimed at making Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050, through a comprehensive set of policies promoting clean energy, sustainable industry, biodiversity protection, and a circular economy.

¹⁶ The Fit for 55 package is a set of legislative proposals by the European Commission aiming to reduce the EU's greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels, as part of the European Green Deal. It revises existing climate and energy laws and introduces new measures to accelerate the transition toward a low-carbon economy across all sectors.

At the construction product level, the Greek market relies on EPDs compliant with EN 15804. While national EPDs remain limited, Greek manufacturers (e.g., Sidenor (steel), KEBE (bricks and roof tiles), and Titan Group (cement and concrete)) are turning to the International EPD System to publish verified EN 15804-based EPDs [61], [62], [63]. Moreover, academic work on a residential LCA case study in Thessaloniki found that due to the absence of a broad national Life-Cycle Inventory (LCI) database, practitioners frequently rely on Ecoinvent datasets and product EPDs as primary data sources (Chastas et al., 2017).

In terms of software and tools, practitioners primarily use international LCA software such as SimaPro, OpenLCA, and GaBi, which offer generic databases and methodologies suitable for regional application [65]. We assume that Greece practitioners follow a similar approach, given the lack of a nationally tailored LCA software ecosystem. Meanwhile, academic research groups, notably at the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), are actively developing localised datasets and case studies to better adapt LCA tools to the Greek climatic and construction context (e.g., [66]).

At the building scale, voluntary use of LCA is mainly driven by green building certification schemes such as LEED, BREEAM, and the Greek Green Building Council's voluntary frameworks (in 2022, 47 LEED-certified projects have been completed in Greece [67]). These certifications encourage the use of LCA to assess environmental impacts, although uptake remains limited to innovative or high-profile projects rather than standard practice. A strong desire to develop environmental assessments on this scale seems to be emerging in the country [68]. The methodology generally aligns with EN 15978, with typical inclusion of stages A1–A3 (product phase), A4–A5 (transport and installation), and C1–C4 (end-of-life). Module D and use-phase modules (B1–B7) are considered optionally depending on project goals. The reference study period is most often set at 50 years.

To date, Greece has not established a standardised regulatory or methodological framework for conducting LCA at the neighbourhood scale. No documented LCA studies at this scale have been identified in the scientific or technical literature.

In summary, while Greece is still in the early stages of integrating LCA into its construction sector, the combination of growing regulatory pressure at the EU level, academic research, and voluntary certification schemes is gradually fostering the adoption of life-cycle thinking.

3.1.6. Germany

In Germany, LCA is embedded in sustainable building certification and public-sector design processes, and since 2023 it has also become mandatory for new buildings within the framework of the federal Qualitätssiegel Nachhaltiges Gebäude (QNG). Beyond these regulatory requirements, LCA is further integrated in voluntary frameworks such as the Bewertungssystem Nachhaltiges Bauen (BNB) [69] and the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Nachhaltiges Bauen (DGNB) certification system [70], both of which require LCA-based assessments aligned with EN 15978.

At the construction product level, Germany relies heavily on EPDs that follow the European standard EN 15804 and ISO 14040/14044. The [German Institut Bauen und Umwelt e.V. \(IBU\)](#) [71] operates one of the largest and most recognised EPD programs in Europe and is a founding member of ECO Platform. The [ÖKOBAUDAT database](#) [72], maintained by the Federal Ministry, centralises LCA data for construction materials and systems used in Germany, including third-party verified EPDs and generic datasets. This database ensures consistency in public projects and forms the basis for BNB and DGNB assessments. Common software such as SimaPro, GaBi, OpenLCA are used in Germany to model these datasets (BBSR, 2024). Also, the public information portal for sustainable building materials [WECOBIS](#)¹⁷ provides neutral, free, and science-based guidance on material selection for sustainable construction. It offers comprehensive fact sheets on a wide range of building materials, covering notably environmental aspects (e.g., life-cycle stages, recyclability, end-of-life) and links to LCA data, including EPDs from IBU and datasets available in ÖKOBAUDAT [73]. Its serves as a decision-support tool to help project stakeholders identify low-impact and also guides users toward suitable datasets and tools for regulatory LCA requirements in Germany.

At the building scale, LCA is mandatory for buildings assessed under the BNB and DGNB systems, especially for public buildings and federal construction projects. Indeed, in 2025 the QNG was introduced, making DGNB Silver certification and result-based carbon thresholds mandatory for projects seeking public subsidies. Notably, QNG includes whole-life carbon thresholds, such as 24 kg CO₂e/m²/year over a 50-year life-cycle for residential buildings [74].

The [eLCA software](#) tool, developed by the Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development (BBSR), is specifically designed for compliance with German sustainability criteria and uses the ÖKOBAUDAT database. The methodology is aligned with EN 15978 and allows for cradle-to-grave analysis (including modules A1–A5, B6, and C1–C4, with optional modules depending on the building type and project scope (e.g., module D is reported separately and increasingly emphasised in design decisions) [75].

At the urban or district scale, Germany is involved in the development of LCA approaches that go beyond individual buildings. The DGNB Urban Districts certification is Germany's leading framework to evaluate and certify sustainable urban developments. It applies to new developments, redevelopments, and even existing urban districts, covering diverse urban forms such as mixed-use areas, business parks, or residential zones. The system goes beyond individual buildings and adopts a comprehensive, systemic approach to urban sustainability, structured around six main criteria groups including environmental quality. It integrates LCA principles but does not impose a fixed methodology [76].

Germany also actively contributes to European harmonisation efforts through the Level(s) framework and the PEF initiative. German experts and institutions play a leading role in standardisation committees (CEN/TC 350) and in the evolution of European LCA methodologies for buildings and construction products [77].

¹⁷ Developed by the Bavarian State Ministry for Housing, Building and Transport in cooperation with the Federal Chamber of German Architects (BAK).

3.1.7. Lithuania

In Lithuania, the adoption of LCA in the construction sector is an emerging practice that is steadily gaining momentum due to growing environmental awareness and alignment with European Union climate and sustainability policies. The country is actively working to integrate LCA methodologies at various scales, although it remains at an early stage. No mandatory national regulation requiring LCA in building projects exists for the moment.

At the construction product level, the availability of nationally developed EPDs remains limited for Lithuania, most stakeholders referring to broader European databases like Ecoinvent [7] or the International EPD System [78] for life-cycle inventory data. Efforts are underway within local industry and academic circles to develop more localised datasets that better represent the specificities of Lithuanian materials and climate conditions (e.g., EPDs from the Peikko company [79]).

At the building scale, LCA remains largely voluntary, with its use encouraged through green building certification schemes such as BREEAM International and LEED, which include life-cycle based material and energy credits [80]. Lithuania has also developed its own national sustainability assessment system (LBSAS) under the Lithuanian Green Building Council (LGBC) [81], which aligns with international frameworks and includes criteria related to embodied carbon and materials use. The LCA methodology applied in is generally based on EN 15978, with a 50-year reference period and include life-cycle stages A1–A3, A4–A5, and C1–C4. Modules B1–B5 and are included on a case-by-case basis. LCA remains mostly applied in innovative or high-profile certified projects, not as a standard procedure across the construction sector.

At the building and product level, LCA remains largely dependent on international tools and databases. Practitioners commonly rely on generic LCA software such as SimaPro for modelling environmental impacts [82].

Regarding district scale LCA, initiatives are currently at a nascent stage, primarily linked to EU-funded projects as the LCA4Regions project which aims to integrate life-cycle methodologies into regional policy tools and green public procurement practices [83].

Lithuania participates in European efforts to harmonise LCA methodologies and databases, such as the Level(s) framework and the development of Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEFCRs). There is a recognised need to improve data interoperability and methodological alignment to enhance the reliability and usability of LCA outcomes in national and regional contexts.

3.1.8. Turkey

In Turkey, LCA is gradually gaining recognition in the construction sector but still is an emerging practice compared to many European countries. Turkey is increasingly aligning with international standards and benefiting from EU-driven sustainability initiatives.

At the construction product scale, stakeholders primarily rely on EPDs developed in accordance with EN 15804, typically issued via EPD Turkey (SURATAM) under the International EPD System [84], [85]. However, the number of Turkey-specific EPDs remains limited. Consequently, practitioners largely depend on generic European or international LCA databases such as Ecoinvent for modelling purposes. To address this gap, efforts are underway to develop locally relevant datasets such as [86]:

- The Turkish Life-Cycle Inventory Database (TLCID) which contain environmental performance data in many different sectors such as building materials, energy, transportation, etc.
- The TurCoMDat LCA database, which offers third-party verified life-cycle data for Turkish materials and systems aligned with international certification frameworks.

At the building scale in Turkey, the use of LCA remains predominantly voluntary, driven mainly through participation in international certification schemes such as LEED and BREEAM (e.g., in 2022, 61 buildings in Turkey are BREEAM-certified [87]), as well as emerging local initiatives like the ÇEDBİK run B.E.S.T. system. These certification frameworks promote the inclusion of LCA-based credits for material selection, embodied carbon evaluation, and energy efficiency in new constructions and renovations [88], [89]. The most common reference study period is 50 years, with life-cycle stages A1–A5 and C1–C4 generally included. The use-phase modules (B1–B7) and module D are less consistently applied. Turkey’s building sector is embracing LCA as a sustainability tool, despite challenges like lack of data and method standardisation [90].

At the district or urban scale, no harmonised national LCA assessment framework exists in Turkey. LCA remains minimally applied in Turkey, mainly driven by academic research and participation in pilot projects, rather than through established national frameworks (e.g., doctoral research project developed a decision support tool for early stage LCA of mass housing neighbourhoods [91]).

Regarding LCA tools, software such as SimaPro, GaBi, and OpenLCA seems to be used in academic and professional circles as no specific LCA tool was found during this state-of-the-art review.

Turkey is engaged in European and international efforts to harmonise LCA methodologies and data standards such as the Level(s) framework.

3.1.9. Switzerland

Switzerland has long been a frontrunner in integrating LCA into the construction sector, supported by its strong scientific infrastructure, advanced environmental policies, and a cultural emphasis on resource efficiency and quality. LCA is widely used at the product, building, and district scales, for voluntary environmental assessment and within public procurement procedures, but it is not mandated by building legislation at the federal level.

At the construction product scale, a major strength of Switzerland lies in its world-renowned database: Ecoinvent, developed by the Ecoinvent Association [7], based in Zurich. It is one

of the most widely used comprehensive and internationally referenced LCI databases in the world, offering more than 1500 building and construction materials datasets [92]. It forms the backbone of many LCA tools used both in Switzerland and other countries, such as SimaPro, OpenLCA, and GaBi.

Also, the SUGB (Swiss Association for the Surveillance of Mineral Construction Materials) is a program part of the ECO Platform to ensure the harmonisation of Swiss-EPDs with standards (EN 15804 and ISO 14025) [93]. The Coordination Conference of Public Sector Construction and Property Services (KBOB) also provides a national reference database tailored to the Swiss context, covering over 250 construction material datasets, building systems, energy supply, transport, and waste services [94].

However, Switzerland does not maintain a centralised national EPD database comparable to France's INIES or Germany's ÖKOBAUDAT.

At the building scale, Switzerland applies LCA through several voluntary sustainability standards, including Minergie-ECO [95] and the Standard Nachhaltiges Bauen Schweiz (SNBS) [96], which encourage or require life-cycle carbon and environmental impact assessments. These certifications promote a life-cycle approach to energy and material flows, as well as climate performance. LCA is generally aligned with European norms such as EN 15978 and EN 15804 but tailored to the Swiss regulatory and environmental context. Also, the Swiss Society of Engineers and Architects (SIA) defines LCA guidelines in standard SIA 2032, which is aligned with EN 15978. The Swiss methodology typically includes life-cycle modules A1–A5, B6, C1–C4, and optionally module D. The standard reference study period is 60 years [97].

Switzerland is also involved in district-scale assessments (e.g., Minergie-District Certification (Minergie, 2025b)) even if no national framework exists. These initiatives are aligned with LCA principles and promoting systemic thinking at the urban level.

While Switzerland is not an EU member, it actively participates in European research and policy initiatives, particularly in alignment with Level(s) and the PEF. Swiss institutions are also involved in developing BIM-LCA integrations and digital tools to assess environmental impacts at early design stages, helping bridge the gap between data-rich LCA models and real-world construction practice [99].

3.1.10. United Kingdom

In the United Kingdom (UK), LCA is increasingly integrated into the construction sector as a tool to evaluate and reduce environmental impacts across the full life cycle of buildings and infrastructure. While there is no national regulation mandating LCA for all construction projects, its application is supported by industry standards, government guidance, and a strong certification and voluntary reporting culture.

At the construction product scale, UK follows the European and international standards EN 15804 and ISO 14040/14044 for the development of EPDs (RICS, 2021; WRAP, 2018). While the

UK does not maintain a centralised national database, several platforms provide EPDs and environmental data, including the UK EPD Programme operated by the BRE [100]. The UK EPD Programme is recognised by the ECO Platform and ensures compliance with EN 15804. The UK also benefits from the Inventory of Carbon and Energy (ICE) database from the University of Bath providing embodied carbon values for construction materials commonly used in the UK context [101].

At the building scale, LCA is frequently integrated within voluntary sustainability certification/guideline schemes such as BREEAM UK [102] or LETI (London Energy Transformation Initiative) [103] which encourage or require LCA for measuring environmental impacts across building life cycles. BREEAM (most widely used building assessment method in the UK), has embedded LCA methodologies, supporting designers and developers in optimising carbon and environmental performance from early design through to operation. The RICS Whole Life Carbon Assessment (WLCA) standard is a guidance document developed by the Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors (RICS) to provide a consistent methodology for assessing the whole life carbon impacts of buildings and infrastructure projects. This methodology follows EN 15978 and ISO 14040/14044, with a 60-year reference study period. Life-cycle stages A1–A5 and C1–C4 are usually required, with optional inclusion of module B (especially B6 and B7 for operational impacts), and increasing attention is being paid to module D [39], [104].

The UK Green Building Council (UKGBC) plays a key role in promoting LCA to facilitate compliance with emerging UK regulations and voluntary targets [105]. The UKGBC Net Zero Carbon Buildings Framework encourage the use of LCA and embodied carbon assessments in line with the UK's net zero targets.

At the district and urban scale, LCA application is still developing, with pilot projects supported under the UK's Net Zero Strategy and initiatives such as:

- The London Plan 2021 that requires whole-life carbon assessments for major developments;
- The Connected Places Catapult¹⁸, which combine LCA with broader sustainability metrics to promote low-carbon, resilient urban development [106].

However, there is no harmonised, mandatory framework for district-level LCA in the UK at present.

Regarding tools and software, practitioners in the UK commonly use international platforms like SimaPro, One Click LCA, and OpenLCA for environmental impact modelling. Challenges remain regarding data accessibility, practitioner training, and harmonisation of methods across sectors.

On the regulatory front, the UK Government's Part Z proposal (currently under discussion) aims to make the measurement and limitation of embodied carbon mandatory for new buildings through whole-life carbon assessments. Although not yet legally adopted, the

¹⁸ Catapult is the UK center of Excellence for Urban Innovation and Mobility.

proposal reflects the growing political consensus on integrating LCA into national regulations [107]. In addition, Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA) is providing embodied carbon target for all building types using Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors (RICS) 970 Whole Life Carbon Assessment (WLCA) methodology for the entire life cycle [108], [109]:

- Less than 13,3 kg CO₂eq/m² in 2025 for new office buildings;
- Less than 675 kg CO₂eq/ m² in 2025 for new building school;
- Less than 800 kg CO₂eq/ m² in 2025 for residential buildings.

The UK participates actively in European harmonisation efforts including Level(s) and the PEF initiative, especially for cross-border projects and product declarations.

3.2. Countries other than the WILSON consortium

3.2.1. Norway

In Norway, LCA has become a widely used tool in the construction sector, especially for low-carbon buildings. Although not yet fully mandatory at the national regulatory level, Norway stands out for its early voluntary integration of LCA into leading public and private construction projects. The country has developed national calculation methodologies and databases, and is progressively moving toward regulatory inclusion, particularly through its strong municipal initiatives and public procurement requirements.

At the product scale, Norway relies heavily on EPDs conforming to EN 15804, published in [EPD Norge](#) [110], [111]. Also, Byggtjeneste, a Norway's leading provider of digital and product data for the construction industry operates the NOBB database (a portal for standardised construction product information across the sector) [112]. These EPDs are developed using standard LCA software like Gabi or SimaPro, with methodological guidance from Norwegian PCR (Product Category Rules) documents [113]. EPDs in Norway are static and focus on cradle-to-gate or cradle-to-grave scopes, depending on the product and PCR. To operationalise LCA, Norway uses a range of dedicated tools, among which One Click LCA is the most prominent [114].

At the building scale, LCA has been formally standardised through NS 3720:2018, a national standard that provides methodological rules for assessing greenhouse gas emissions from buildings over their life cycle [115]. NS 3720 aligns with ISO 14040/14044 and EN 15978 (modules A1–A5, B4–B7, C1–C4, and D), while introducing specific requirements adapted to the Norwegian context, such as the consideration of energy-related emissions from building operation and detailed accounting of transport and construction processes. The standard applies to both new buildings and renovations and seems to be widely adopted in the sector.

At the neighbourhood and district scales, Norway is also making progress. Pilot projects in Oslo and Trondheim, often supported by SINTEF¹⁹, have begun testing district-level carbon

¹⁹ SINTEF is one of Europe's largest independent research organisations, based in Norway, specialising in applied research across technology, natural sciences, and social sciences. It collaborates closely with industry and government to develop innovative, science-based solutions for sustainable development, including in energy, construction, and urban planning.

accounting, linking infrastructure emissions, transport, and building performance [116]. These efforts feed into national and EU-level research, such as the Horizon Europe ARV project, in which Norway is a key partner [117].

Finally, Norway actively contributes to European harmonisation via ECO Platform, Level(s), and Nordic collaborations on circularity and embodied carbon.

3.2.2. Denmark

In Denmark, LCA has recently gained regulatory status within the national building code, making it one of the most advanced European countries in terms of integrating environmental performance into construction regulations. Since January 2023, all new buildings in Denmark must document their climate impact over a 50-year life cycle, marking a significant shift from voluntary to mandatory use of LCA at the building scale [118].

At the construction product scale, construction stakeholders rely on EPDs compliant with EN 15804 for the environmental data inputs to LCA. EPDs are standardised, third-party verified documents that report a product's life cycle impacts according to common rules. In Denmark, the official programme operator for building material EPDs is EPD Danmark [119]. Additionally, Denmark recognises EPDs from international or other programs via mutual agreements (e.g., INIES, IBU). These EPDs are static and calculated with standard LCA software. Danish construction actors are encouraged to use specific EPDs over generic data to improve accuracy²⁰ [120].

At the building scale, LCA in Denmark follows the methodology outlined in EN 15978 and ISO 14040/14044, with national guidance provided by the Danish Transport and Construction Agency. The methodology covers life-cycle stages A1 to C4 (product, construction, use, and end of life), with module D (beyond the system boundary, e.g., recycling benefits) reported separately [39], [121]. The carbon impact is calculated based on material quantities, construction and transport processes, operational energy and water use, and demolition scenarios. The [LCAbyg tool](#) is used in Denmark to assess buildings and it supports import of EPDs (LCAbyg, 2025).

At the regulatory level, the Danish Building Regulations introduced a national requirement for carbon accounting based on LCA [123]. For all new buildings above 1,000 m², a GHG emission limit of 12 kgCO₂e/m²/year applies (calculated over a 50-year reference period), while all new buildings must submit a life cycle carbon calculation (regardless of size) [108], [124]. This approach is performance-based, encouraging innovation and optimisation, while fostering market readiness for stricter thresholds in the future. A gradual tightening of carbon limits is already planned for the coming years, following a roadmap to 2029.

Beyond the individual building scale, Denmark is exploring LCA applications at district and urban levels. Research institutions like the Danish Building Research Institute (SBI²¹) and

²⁰ Studies by the Danish Building Research Institute (SBI/BUILD) have shown that replacing generic data with EPD data can change the LCA outcomes and help identify more realistic improvement options.

²¹ Statens Byggeforskningsinstitut

Aalborg University, as well as public agencies, are involved in pilot studies to assess climate impacts of infrastructure, mobility, and public spaces. These approaches aim to anticipate future urban-scale climate accounting, in line with EU goals on sustainable built environments [125].

Several digital tools have been adapted or developed for the Danish context, including LCAByg, the official national tool maintained by the SBI. LCAByg is freely available, regularly updated to reflect changes in regulation, and linked to a national database of generic and specific environmental data, including EPDs. Also, EG Construction provides software [EG Sigma](#) / EG SmartKalk that are able to calculate both price and carbon emissions of a building [126], [127]. Other tools used include One Click LCA, SimaPro, and Gabi, particularly for projects aiming at higher-level environmental certifications such as DGNB-DK or Nordic Swan.

As part of the Nordic Sustainable Construction programme (2021–2024), Denmark participated in the “Nordic Harmonisation of Life Cycle Assessment” work package, which developed a roadmap for aligning national LCA methods, limit values, and digital tools across Nordic countries [128]. Beyond Nordic frameworks, Denmark contributes to EU harmonisation efforts through active participation in Level(s) and ECO Platform. The country is also monitoring the development of PEFCRs, aiming to ensure future compatibility with EU-wide digital data systems [129].

3.2.3. Sweden

In Sweden, LCA is progressively becoming an essential component of the national strategy for reducing GHG emissions in the construction sector. While LCA was historically used in voluntary certification schemes and research, a significant regulatory shift occurred with the adoption of the Klimatdeklaration (Climate Declaration) for new buildings, which came into force on 1 January 2022. This regulation marks the first national step towards making carbon reporting mandatory at the building level, based on LCA principles.

At the product level, LCA relies on EPDs aligned with EN 15804 and ISO 14040/14044, and managed by EPD International AB [130]²², a key Swedish operator of the International EPD System, one of the world’s largest EPD programmes. Many Swedish manufacturers publish verified EPDs to support both domestic compliance and exports. These EPDs are created using professional LCA software such as SimaPro, Gabi, or openLCA, and are stored in international databases.

The [Klimatdatabasen](#) maintained by Boverket²³ provides generic climate data (emission factors) for construction materials and related processes when specific EPDs are not available. This ensures transparency by requiring values to be conservatively set (e.g., about

²² Originally founded in Sweden in 1998 by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, this programme is now one of the world’s largest EPD frameworks and requires third-party verification according to ISO 14025, EN 15804, and ISO 21930.

²³ The Swedish National Board of Housing, Building and Planning

25 % higher than average EPD-based emissions) thereby encouraging the use of product-specific data where possible [131], [132].

At the building level, the Klimatdeklaration requires developers to quantify carbon impacts using approved calculation tools, many of which interface with databases of generic or product-specific LCA profiles. Widely used tool is BM (Byggsektorns Miljöberäkningsverktyg), developed by IVL (Swedish Environmental Research Institute on behalf of the Swedish Energy Agency) [133].

Under the Climate Declaration Act, all new buildings above 100 m² (residential and non-residential) must report their climate impact over the life cycle, based on a 50-year reference study period, focusing on stages A1–A5 (product and construction phase) [39]. Modules B, C, and D are currently optional but are expected to be integrated in the coming phases of the regulation. The goal is to gradually introduce carbon thresholds (expected around 2027–2028) and eventually cover the full life cycle. This roadmap is part of Sweden's broader commitment to achieve net zero GHG emissions by 2045 [134].

A key feature of the Swedish system is that results of each Climate Declaration are submitted to a national database managed by Boverket. This enables policy makers to monitor the climate impact of the building stock and adjust thresholds accordingly. Boverket also provides regular statistics and analysis, helping to build a comprehensive reference base for the sector. As of 2024, 1041 projects have been registered [135].

Beyond individual buildings, Sweden is a pioneer of urban-scale environmental assessment. Several municipalities (e.g., Malmö, Gothenburg, Stockholm) have implemented district LCA approaches or climate budgeting tools for urban development [136], [137], [138].

Sweden also plays an active role in European harmonisation efforts. Swedish experts contribute to the Level(s) framework, CEN/TC 350, and PEF development.

3.2.4. Finland

In Finland, LCA is increasingly recognised as a key tool to achieve the country's ambitious climate goals, especially in the building sector, which accounts for a significant share of national greenhouse gas emissions. The Finnish Ministry of the Environment and the Finnish Green Building Council (FIGBC) have actively promoted LCA as part of the country's sustainability roadmap, aligning with the European Green Deal and national carbon neutrality targets set for 2035 [139].

At the product level, Finland relies on EPDs published via Environdec, IBU, or other ECO Platform members, as Finland does not operate its own national EPD program. Nevertheless, Finland is capitalising on its environmental data in the [CO2data.fi database](https://co2data.fi) [140]. Manufacturers are encouraged to declare environmental impacts through these schemes, especially in public procurement or for certifications like RT EPD, LEED, or BREEAM. Thus, many Finnish manufacturers produce verified EPDs, particularly for timber products, a dominant

construction material in Finland due to the country's large forest resources (e.g., Metsä [141] and Luvian Saha [142]).

At the building scale, Finland is actively integrating LCA into its construction policy, with mandatory carbon footprint reporting for new buildings (residential and non-residential) entered into force at the beginning of 2025. A voluntary carbon calculation method, based on EN 15978 and developed by the Ministry of the Environment, has been in use since 2019 and tested in several real projects [143]. The Finnish methodology typically includes life-cycle stages A1–A5, B4, B6, C1–C4, and optionally D. The reference study period is set at 50 years.

At the district scale, Finnish municipalities (e.g., Helsinki, Lahti, Tampere) have launched pilot projects integrating LCA into urban-scale sustainability planning, often in collaboration with Smart Cities, Circular Economy platforms, and EU-funded programs (e.g., SPARCS [144], STARDUST [145]). These initiatives explore links between LCA, energy systems, material flows, and nature-based solutions. Although there is no regulatory obligation yet, these approaches are gaining traction in strategic planning.

Finland seems to actively contribute to European harmonisation initiatives such as the Level(s) framework, CEN/TC 350, and the PEF development. Finnish experts emphasise the importance of data interoperability and methodological consistency to facilitate the scaling up of LCA use across the construction sector [128].

3.3. Comparative analysis: LCA practices

3.3.1. Construction product scale

The state-of-the-art reveals that almost all countries rely on EPDs compliant with EN 15804, and many contribute to or recognise ECO Platform verified declarations. Only a few countries (e.g., Denmark, Germany, France, Sweden) operate their own accredited national EPD programs.

LCA at the scale of construction products is now largely standardised at the European level. Since 2012, the EN 15804 standard has defined common rules for EPDs that quantify the “cradle-to-grave” impacts of construction materials. As a result, most European countries use EPDs compliant with EN 15804 to communicate the environmental footprint of materials. This standardisation has significantly harmonised product-level LCA practices: EPDs provide transparent and comparable information on the life cycle impacts of products, enabling manufacturers to showcase their environmental performance and allowing professionals to compare products on an objective basis.

The role of the ECO Platform, which brings together European EPD programme operators, should also be highlighted, as it helps ensure mutual recognition of EPDs that comply with the relevant standards, even though each country can develop its own national database (e.g., INIES in France, Ökobaudat in Germany) and declaration programmes. These differences in implementation remain minor compared to the strong common framework now in place.

3.3.2. Building scale

The state of the art reveals a growing convergence toward the use of standardised methodologies (EN 15978), as building LCA is driven by climate goals (such as the Paris Agreement and carbon neutrality targets) and emerging national regulations. However, significant disparities remain in the level of regulatory enforcement, scope, technical maturity, and the application of the EN 15978 across countries.

Each country has developed its own building LCA methodology or regulation, leading to significant differences in scope and results between nations. While the building LCA methods are all inspired by EN 15978, the standard left substantial room for interpretation (e.g., system boundaries, included life-cycle modules), which has resulted in considerable variations in outcomes across Europe. The adoption and implementation of building LCA differ widely throughout Europe, making cross-country comparisons difficult and hindering the development of common benchmarks [146].

Over the past five years, those countries have introduced LCA requirements for new buildings, often including thresholds in kg CO₂/m² or in €/ (m².an). However, the scope (e.g., covered life-cycle modules), reference study period, chosen indicators, and compliance mechanisms still vary greatly from one country to another.

A useful way to classify countries is according to the level of regulatory constraint:

- Countries with mandatory LCA including quantitative thresholds: Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Norway, Netherlands, France and Germany have set binding carbon caps or shadow price limit;
- Countries with voluntary schemes or pilot programs: Italy, Spain, Greece, Turkey, Lithuania, and the United Kingdom mainly promote LCA through voluntary frameworks, EU-funded pilots, or industry-led initiatives, with no nationwide legal obligation to date.

Regarding tools, One Click LCA has become a dominant platform in Europe due to its integration capabilities and alignment with certification systems. However, most countries have developed or adopted national tools to ensure consistency with local practices and databases (e.g., LCabyg, CO₂data.fi, eLCA, ElodiebyCype, etc.).

3.3.3. District scale

At the district or urban territory scale, LCA is less mature than at the building level, but emerging initiatives are appearing across Europe. There is currently no unified European standard equivalent to EN 15978 for districts. However, several national methodologies and R&D projects have emerged, such as the “Quartier Énergie Carbone” method and the UrbanPrint tool, both developed in France. Other countries are also exploring territorial LCA through pilot projects, although these are often limited to a few indicators (e.g., embodied energy, carbon). Also, most countries are in an experimental phase, testing LCA integration into urban-scale planning through EU projects (e.g., Horizon Europe, Level(s) pilots, etc.).

Despite these advancements, practices remain fragmented and experimental. Each methodology may define its own scope, making cross-country or cross-project comparison difficult. A key challenge is the lack of reliable urban-scale data, particularly concerning infrastructure impacts or users' mobility patterns.

Nevertheless, the strategic value of district-scale LCA is clear: it helps avoid impact shifting between buildings and their urban context (e.g., ensuring that a highly energy-efficient building is not only reachable by car, which would offset part of the environmental gains). This holistic approach supports public decision-makers in optimising low-carbon urban planning.

3.3.4. Synthesis of LCA practices and limitations

In this section, we provide a summary table (cf. Table 1) compiling key information for the 14 countries reviewed in the state-of-the-art analysis. The focus is placed on the building scale, as it encompasses initiatives related to construction product assessments.

Table 1: Comparative table of LCA practices in Europe at the building scale

Countries	LCA mandatory	Mandatory LCA scope	Life span (year)	Modules Included	Main tools	EPD program used
Spain	No (voluntary)	Public tenders & cert	50–60	A1–A5, often B4, B6, C	SimaPro, VERDE, OneClickLCA	DAPcons, EPD Spain, Environdec
France	Yes (2022)	All new buildings	50	A1–A5, B4, B6, C1–C4, D	ElodiebyCYpe, Perrenoud	INIES
Netherland	Yes (2013)	All new buildings	50	A1–C4 + D reported separately	MPG, DuboCalc, OneClickLCA	MRPI, ECO Platform
Italy	No (Drafted)	Public projects	50	A1–A5	OpenLCA, SimaPro	EPDItaly, ECO Platform
Greece	No (voluntary)	Limited to pilots	50	A1–A5 (if used)	OpenLCA	ECO Platform
Germany	Yes (2025)	Public buildings	50	A1–C4 + D	eLCA, OneClickLCA	IBU
Lithuania	No (emerging)	EU funded projects	50	A1–A5	OneClickLCA	ECO Platform, Environdec
Turkey	No	Voluntary	50	A1–A5	SimaPro, OneClickLCA	EPD Turkey
Switzerland	No	Public	50	A1–C4	SIA Eco, KBOB tools	KBOB, ECO Platform
United Kingdom	No (proposed)	Voluntary (Part Z)	60	A1–A5 + B4, C, D	OneClickLCA, eTool	BRE, IBU, Environdec
Norway	No	Public and future built	60	A1–C4, D optional	OneClickLCA	EPD Norge
Denmark	Yes (2023)	All new buildings	50	A1–C4, D separate	LCAByg	EPD Danmark
Sweden	Yes (2022)	All new buildings	50	A1–A5 mandatory, others optional	BM, eTool	Environdec
Finland	Yes (2025)	Will be mandatory	50	A1–A5, B4, B6, C1–C4, D	CO2data.fi	Environdec, IBU

Our cross-country review of building LCA methodologies highlighted some inconsistencies and shortcomings. A key finding was that while national frameworks across Europe emphasise reducing carbon and other global impacts, none explicitly account for local biodiversity or ecosystem services. In practice, European standards like EN 15978/15804 do not provide methods to assess biodiversity. The regulatory LCA tools prioritize climate indicators (e.g., Global Warming Potential), while largely ignoring ecological impacts. Consequently, design choices that affect habitats, green space, or biodiversity are not captured by standard LCA results. Our analysis thus revealed a critical gap: decision-makers lack a comprehensive metric to evaluate both a building's negative environmental impacts and its potential positive contributions to local ecosystems.

Moreover, the scope of conventional LCA is mostly global, focusing on issues like GHG emissions, ozone depletion, or acidification. These indicators, although important, fail to reflect local biophysical changes such as soil sealing or urban biodiversity loss. Existing LCA metrics for land use or ecosystem quality are too generic (they aggregate complex ecological effects into a single score, offering little insight into urban nature conservation).

Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) (e.g., green roofs, urban wetlands, tree plantings) pose a special challenge: their environmental cost (materials, maintenance, etc.) are counted in LCA, but their co-benefits (cooling, flood mitigation, pollinator habitat) are not. In conventional LCA and EPDs, a green roof might only show up as extra material impact, with no credit for the ecosystem services it provides. This imbalance creates a blind spot where "grey" infrastructure can seem preferable to "green" alternatives, simply because the LCA ignores the benefits of the latter. Current building assessments focus on climate neutrality and overlook biodiversity, even though biodiversity loss is as urgent as climate change. In summary, our review underscored that traditional LCA tools are insufficient for holistic sustainable design, as they leave out local ecology and positive nature-based contributions.

Given these limitations, there is a growing consensus in both policy and academic circles that current assessment frameworks need to evolve. International and EU-level initiatives increasingly call for methodologies that integrate biodiversity and ecosystem services alongside carbon in planning and decision-making. These evolving expectations reflect a shift in ambition: urban systems are now expected not only to reduce their carbon footprint, but also to actively contribute to nature restoration and ecosystem health. In this context, an integrated assessment approach, that accounts for both negative environmental impacts and positive ecological contributions, is becoming essential for guiding sustainable urban development.

Conversely, many studies on NBS highlight the ecosystem services provided by green infrastructure and often overlook their life-cycle impacts (while conventional LCAs tend to do the opposite). Bridging this methodological gap is essential for a comprehensive sustainability assessment. In practical terms, this means developing approaches capable of quantifying both trade-offs and synergies.

The goal is to equip planners and decision-makers with tools that allow for a fair comparison between grey and green infrastructure, using a unified framework that integrates both “pressure” indicators (e.g., emissions, pollution, resource depletion) and “benefit” indicators (e.g., cooling effects, habitat creation, stormwater regulation).

The HIBOU method was chosen for the WILSON project precisely because it addresses these gaps. Developed by CSTB as an integrated “hybrid” assessment for urban projects, HIBOU extends traditional LCA by incorporating biodiversity and ecosystem service metrics alongside the usual LCA environmental indicators. In contrast to standard building LCA, HIBOU evaluates:

- Impacts on in-situ and ex-situ biodiversity through pressure indicators: climate change, land use, pollution, resources overexploitation;
- Benefits from NBS, such as, urban heat island regulation and biodiversity support.

These go far beyond the “climate change” and “land use” metric in conventional LCA, capturing how a project affects environment locally and globally. Thus, if an urban design includes features like parks, green roofs, or permeable surfaces, HIBOU will credit both, their environmental cost and their ecosystem services in the assessment.

In short, HIBOU fills the gap our review identified by providing the extended framework that current LCA practice lacks. It brings consistency and breadth: consistency by using life-cycle thinking for both standard impacts and new ecological indicators (e.g., ex-situ biodiversity), and breadth by covering issues from climate change to biodiversity in one method.

The following part aims to present the general methodology of HIBOU and the indicators we have selected for the WILSON project to assess the buildings impacts linked to the non-energy uses: climate change and biodiversity nexus.

4. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH TO ASSESS THE NEXUS BETWEEN CLIMATE CHANGE AND BIODIVERSITY (NON-ENERGY USES)

4.1. HIBOU Method – general framework

Local authorities, developers, and construction stakeholders are facing increasing pressure to integrate environmental considerations into their urban projects. They must simultaneously address carbon neutrality targets (sometimes embedded in a regulatory framework (cf. Part 3)), preserve biodiversity, manage water sustainably, mitigate urban heat islands, and ensure a living environment that supports residents' health and well-being. On top of these institutional and societal expectations, there is an increasing demand for transparency and accountability: stakeholders are now required to objectively demonstrate both the positive and negative impacts of their projects. Yet, to guide their decisions and trade-offs, they still lack tools that can capture, in an integrated, quantitative, and operational way, the real effects of developments across all urban challenges.

At the European level, numerous studies highlight this gap between the strategic importance of environmental issues and the weakness of the operational tools available to assess them [147], [148]²⁴. In France, for instance, the Baromètre de l'Immobilier Durable published by the Observatoire de l'Immobilier Durable (OID) in 2020 showed that while 93% of real estate asset managers had set objectives regarding energy, and 90% regarding greenhouse gas emissions, only 34% had dedicated indicators for biodiversity [149]. This trend, observed in France, mirrors a broader European dynamic where issues such as biodiversity, water cycles, or quality of life remain less equipped and less systematically measured compared to climate and energy. Similarly, the national survey "Bâtiment et biodiversité" conducted by the Ministry of Ecological Transition (with over 700 responses) revealed that more than half of the stakeholders facing biodiversity challenges struggled to find operational solutions [150]. This situation is also observed in other European countries facing similar constraints.

In the absence of robust and harmonised methods, the implementation of so-called "sustainable" developments still too often relies on qualitative requirements ("enhance biodiversity," "improve quality of life") without any real capacity to objectify and compare outcomes. Therefore, the need for integrated, reliable, and scalable assessment tools has become a central issue for public and private decision-makers across Europe, to align with demonstrated synergies and trade-offs between biodiversity protection and climate change mitigation and adaptation [151].

It is precisely to address this need that CSTB is developing the HIBOU method (INN 6). Designed as an operational science-based tool, it aims to move beyond qualitative or domain-specific approaches by providing an integrated, objective, and multi-criteria assessment of urban development projects [152].

²⁴ Highlighting two key gaps: the absence of tools covering the scale of district or cities, and assessments often focused on energy, mobility or buildings, without a multi-issue systemic vision.

HIBOU method is designed to be deployed across different scales (building, plot, district, city, territory) in a coherent manner, relying on a common set of indicators and criteria. This continuity across scales makes it possible to consolidate and aggregate results, thereby providing an integrated view of the environmental and social performance of a project, regardless of the level of analysis. The method is intended to support urban planning and construction stakeholders, whether or not they are experts in the urban issues it addresses. It enables:

- Diagnosing projects at the pre-design stage in order to identify key challenges;
- Supporting the design process to guide future planning choices by:
 - Integrating the site-specific issues identified during the diagnostic phase;
 - Allowing comparison between different planning options (ex: with or without NBS);
 - Monitoring the achievement of objectives throughout the implementation and operational phases.

Its purpose is to evaluate a wide range of projects, including urban expansion operations, urban renewal (e.g., reuse of brownfields, transformation of underutilised spaces), public space improvements, renaturation/de-sealing projects (e.g., renovation of schoolyards), temporary or transitional developments (tactical urbanism), as well as new construction or building renovation. At the territorial scale, the method can also support urban planning processes.

The method evaluates projects integrating NBS, but also their alternatives (e.g., green roof vs. gravel roof), in order to guide choices toward the most suitable solutions for a given local context. By enabling the comparison of different planning options through a harmonised, multi-criteria approach, HIBOU supports informed decision-making, ensuring that all urban issues are considered with the same level of importance (e.g., biodiversity, water resources, as well as health and well-being, are given equal consideration alongside energy use and climate change). The urban challenges addressed in the HIBOU method are presented in Figure 2²⁵.

²⁵ Stakeholders can choose to apply the HIBOU method to all the issues it addresses, or only to a subset of them.

Figure 2 : Urban challenges addressed by the HIBOU method

The deployment of the HIBOU method is structured around several components, illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 : HIBOU method modules

The “Indicators” module is central to the method. The added value of the HIBOU indicators is reflected in the following characteristics:

- **Integrated and multi-criteria:** existing tools often assess urban challenges independently, which can lead to fragmented solutions. HIBOU stands out by offering an integrated evaluation, enabling design stakeholders to understand the interactions between these different issues and to develop coherent strategies for their projects.
- **Objective and transparent:** qualitative methods, while valuable, can lack precision and allow subjective interpretation. By relying on quantitative indicators, the HIBOU method provides enhanced objectivity, allowing projects to be compared based on measurable and verifiable criteria.
- **Adapted to territorial specificities:** unlike many uniform approaches, HIBOU takes into account project-specific constraints (e.g., presence of a historic monument can limit interventions) as well as local environmental characteristics (rainfall, climatic data, regional ecological inventories). This contextualisation enables realistic evaluations that are directly actionable for local stakeholders.

The digital tools availability (“Digital Tools” module), including databases are also essential for the operational use. Indeed, implementing user-friendly digital tools with feasible input data requirements would allow them to adopt the method without needing significant upskilling on each subject.

The field testing of the method (“Application” module) is crucial to assess the robustness of calculations, the relevance of selected indicators, and the usability of associated digital tools. This component ensures that HIBOU remains a pragmatic, operational method aligned with stakeholders’ expectations.

Widespread use of the HIBOU method will help establish reference values and trajectories (“Trajectories” module) for the challenges it addresses, tailored to project types and urban contexts, particularly where benchmarks are lacking (e.g., biodiversity). By providing quantitative reference points, it can support public authorities in defining clear, measurable objectives, thereby promoting more sustainable urban development and a better-managed ecological transition (“Communication” module).

4.2. HIBOU’s KPIs selected for the WILSON project

4.2.1. KPIs presentation

As previously mentioned, within the WILSON project it is proposed to address the urban challenges of “Environmental Footprint” and “In-situ Biodiversity”. For both issues, the HIBOU methodology provides a family of indicators, from among which the following have been selected (cf. *Deliverable 4.5*²⁶ of the WILSON project):

- The Global Warming Potential (GWP) indicator to assess climate change impacts;
- Six LCA indicators evaluating the impacts on ex-situ biodiversity;
- The Harmonised Biotope Area Factor (BAFh) to measure impacts on in-situ biodiversity.

The following sub-sections introduce these indicators.

Climate change – Global Warming Potential (GWP)

Within the HIBOU framework, the indicator used to reflect climate change is the GWP. The GWP indicator measures the climate warming potential associated with GHG emissions generated by a product, building, or project over its entire life cycle. It is calculated within the framework of a LCA according to ISO 14040/14044 standards (general LCA) and European standards EN 15804 (construction products LCA) and EN 15978 (building LCA), ensuring a rigorous and reproducible methodology. The calculation is based on a comprehensive inventory of material and energy flows, including:

- The materials and components used;
- Transportation;
- The use phase;
- Maintenance;
- End-of-life (recycling, recovery, incineration, or landfill).

For urban systems, the calculation is generally carried out over a reference lifespan of 50 years, covering the construction, use, and end-of-life phases. The indicator thus includes all relevant life-cycle stages and allows for the comparison of different planning or

²⁶ <https://wilson-project.eu/events-and-news/wp4-outcomes-laying-the-technical-foundations-for-wilsons-digital-innovation/>

construction options. It accounts for multiple GHG categories, follows a “cradle-to-grave” scope, and uses data from European LCA databases (e.g., Ecoinvent, ELCD) or local inventories.

Input data include material quantities, energy consumption, transport distances and modes, maintenance frequencies, and end-of-life scenarios. These data can be drawn from generic datasets (INIES, Ecoinvent, ELCD). The calculation consists in associating each elementary flow with an emission factor (kg CO₂eq/unit) based on characterisation factors provided by the IPCC over a 100-year horizon. The sum of all flows across the life cycle gives the total GWP. The main output is expressed as a cumulative value of GHG emissions (kg CO₂eq) over the defined reference period. In the HIBOU framework, results can be reported per functional unit (e.g., kg CO₂eq per m².y of a project), enabling cross-comparisons between scales and options.

Within the HIBOU method, the GWP indicator is calculated according to the French RE 2020 framework (cf. section 3.1.2), which defines the rules, assumptions, and databases to be used for the carbon assessment of buildings and urban projects in France. The approach is consistent with the EN standard EN 15978 (building LCA) and the databases specific to the French territory. This includes data on materials (INIES databases), energy mix, and end-of-life scenarios in line with French practices. This approach:

- Ensures compliance with French regulations, without hindering comparisons in a European context, where usage conditions, energy mix, and materials may vary between countries. Indeed, the calculation tools used (such as COMENV²⁷) can integrate configured datasets not included in the INIES database, while still enabling us to provide the product’s environmental profile. The only requirement is that the data comply with the prescribed format;
- Guarantees traceability and reproducibility of results, which are essential for a collaborative European project such as WILSON.

Ex-situ biodiversity

Within the HIBOU framework, biodiversity impacts are addressed through life cycle-based ex-situ indicators, which capture the potential pressures exerted by a project on ecosystems located outside the project boundaries (e.g., through resource extraction, energy production, or emissions along the supply chain). These indicators are still under development at European and international level, but several consensual approaches exist.

The calculation is carried out within the framework of an LCA according to ISO 14040/14044 standards and emerging guidance such as the UNEP-SETAC Life Cycle Initiative or the European Commission’s Environmental Footprint framework [153], [154], [155], [156]. The aim is to quantify how resource use and pollutant emissions contribute to biodiversity loss

²⁷ COMENV is the official calculation engine, developed with the support of the French government and CSTB, for conducting LCA of buildings under the RE2020 environmental regulation. It serves as the standard for evaluating the environmental performance indicators of new constructions according to European standards (EN 15 804 and EN 15 978).

through mechanisms such as land occupation and transformation, climate change, eutrophication, acidification, or ecotoxicity.

In LCA practice, two levels of impact assessment are distinguished: “midpoint” indicators, which represent environmental pressures at an intermediate stage (e.g., CO₂ emissions, nutrient release), and “endpoint” indicators, which translate these pressures into damage on areas of protection such as human health, ecosystems or resources. Biodiversity indicators belong to the endpoint category, as they express the final consequences of multiple pressures in terms of species loss or ecosystem quality degradation.

To calculate impact on ex-situ biodiversity, input data usually include land use (area, duration, type of land cover), pollutant emissions to air, water and soil (e.g., nitrogen, phosphorus, heavy metals, pesticides), and resource extraction (e.g., timber, minerals, fossil fuels). These flows are typically drawn from LCA databases such as Ecoinvent or ELCD. The calculation links these pressures to ecological impact pathways using characterisation models. The main outputs are expressed in biodiversity-relevant units, such as species·year (a proxy for the potential loss of species over a given area and duration) or PDF·m²·year (potentially disappeared fraction of species per surface and time).

Within the HIBOU method, ex-situ biodiversity indicators are not directly calculated from raw inventory data but are predicted from LCA midpoint indicators already computed according to the French RE2020 framework (e.g., climate change, eutrophication, acidification, etc.) (cf. Figure 4). To achieve this, HIBOU relies on corrected characterisation factors derived from the ReCiPe 2016 method. These corrected factors have been obtained through linear regression models (OLS type) trained on reference learning databases, ensuring consistency between RE2020-compatible midpoint results and biodiversity-relevant endpoint predictions. Models are given in Annex 1.

This approach, based on midpoint calculations aligned with European LCA standards, facilitates indicator computation: if an actor already has an LCA model following these standards, the midpoint results can directly be used as input without recalculating the entire LCA from scratch. Among LCA biodiversity endpoint indicators, we are able to successfully predict six indicators:

- Global Warning for Terrestrial Ecosystem (GWTE);
- Global Warning for Freshwater Ecosystem (GWFE);
- Terrestrial Acidification (TA);
- Freshwater Eutrophication (FWEP);
- Water consumption for Terrestrial ecosystem (WCTE);
- Water consumption for aquatic ecosystems (WCAE).

Figure 4 : Ex-situ biodiversity toolchain in HIBOU method

All these indicators are expressed in PDF·m²·year (loss of species richness), the unit recommended by CEN/TC 350 for biodiversity endpoint assessment [156]. This unit facilitates cross-comparisons between different projects scenarios. Ex-situ biodiversity indicators are used to complement on-site biodiversity assessments (in-situ biodiversity indicators) by capturing indirect pressures that occur outside the project perimeter. This dual perspective helps project stakeholders avoid “burden shifting” (e.g., reducing local impacts while increasing remote ones) and supports more holistic decision-making.

In-situ biodiversity – Harmonised Biotope Area Factor (BAFh)

Within the HIBOU framework, in-situ biodiversity is assessed using the BAFh, a French standardised indicator co-developed at the national level to evaluate a project’s capacity to support biodiversity. The BAFh builds upon the principle of the Biotope Area Factor (BAF), widely used in European cities such as Berlin and Helsinki. However, traditional BAF indicators often focus primarily on water infiltration capacity rather than ecological value. In contrast, the BAFh provides a new harmonised nomenclature, detailed enough to characterise the mosaic of land uses within an urban context. This nomenclature is compatible with other European classification systems (e.g., EUNIS), facilitating international comparisons and integration.

The nomenclature includes 41 distinct land use typologies (cf. Annex 2), which account for substrate depth as well as combinations of supported vegetation layers (sedums, herbaceous plants, shrubs, and trees). Each typology is associated with a fixed biotope coefficient ranging from 0 to 1, reflecting its relative contribution to biodiversity: 0 indicates no ecological capacity, whereas 1 represents conditions similar to a natural habitat. The formula for calculating BAFh is given in Figure 5 below.

Harmonised Biotope Area Factor (BAFh)

$$BAFh = \frac{\sum_i^n \text{Area of the land use typologie } i \times \text{Biotope coefficient } i}{\text{Total area}}$$

Figure 5 : Example of land use typologies and BAFh calculation formula

The BAFh was co-developed over five years within a national working group led by CSTB and comprising over 170 stakeholders (associations, urban planners, ecologists, biodiversity label representatives, architects, etc.). All participants shared the goal of creating an indicator that evaluates biodiversity for its intrinsic ecological value and that can be integrated into future environmental regulations. Indeed, the BAFh was developed under Working Group 7 on Biodiversity²⁸, one of nine groups in the CAP 2030 project²⁹, which aims to integrate new environmental themes (beyond carbon and energy) into French urban regulation (future RE 2020). This makes the BAFh particularly relevant for testing in European projects such as WILSON, where it provides a robust tool to assess in-situ biodiversity.

The BAFh enables project stakeholders to quantify the ecologically functional share of a site and compare design alternatives (e.g., gravel roof versus green roof). Within HIBOU, the BAFh plays a role in linking urban planning decisions to ecological outcomes, as it allows for:

- Spatially explicit assessment of habitats and green infrastructure, enabling comparisons between different scenarios of a project;
- Performance-based evaluation: the calculation is made before and after the project to assess the level of the impact;
- Multi-scale application, from the building/plot level to the district or city level, allowing aggregation.

²⁸ <https://www.planbatimentdurable.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/gt-biodiversite-a1638.html>

²⁹ <https://www.planbatimentdurable.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/presentation-generale-a1641.html>

By integrating the BAFh with other indicators (climate change, ex-situ biodiversity, UHI (cf. D12.1)), the HIBOU method provides a complementary perspective: while LCA captures indirect and global pressures, the BAFh focuses on the direct ecological capacity of the project site, offering urban planners actionable insights to maximise biodiversity benefits within their designs.

4.2.2. Data gathering

General workflow

To calculate HIBOU's KPIs, two types of data are required:

- Building data: materials used in construction, equipment, resource consumption, and other relevant characteristics;
- Outdoor data: including land use, materials used for pavements and urban furniture, water consumption for irrigation, and similar information.

For comparison purposes, data must be collected as follows:

- For climate change and ex-situ biodiversity: for the AS-IS scenario (currently designed, as agreed with public authorities) and the TO-BE scenario (theoretical alternatives to the AS-IS scenario, incorporating NBS such as green roofs or green spaces);
- For in-situ biodiversity: for the AS-IS and TO-BE scenarios, as well as for the baseline/current state, to ensure a robust ecological assessment³⁰.

A complete inventory of all flows associated with the building or urban system under study is necessary to calculate HIBOU's KPIs accurately. This includes materials, equipment, and energy and water consumption throughout the life cycle, covering type, quantity, properties, and lifespan. At the scale of an urban project, this data collection is a massive task. To simplify this process without compromising the accuracy of the KPIs used in the WILSON project, CSTB has developed tools that facilitate data gathering and provide a data enrichment service. This approach for data collection and enrichment is detailed in the *Deliverable 9.4*. The general workflow is summarised in Figure 6 below.

³⁰ In-situ biodiversity requires a third reference level (the current baseline) to capture the ecological trajectory of the site and avoid misinterpreting gains or losses.

Figure 6 : Schematic representation of the toolchain from data collection to HIBOU KPIs calculation

Figure 6 illustrates the link between the data collection process (carried out in the framework of the Task 9.4, see Deliverable 9.4), and the calculation of the HIBOU KPIs. As described in detail in the *Deliverable 9.4 - Material passports for sustainable renovations – Month 18*, the data are collected from different sources (BIM models, Excel files and Web forms), in order to create a structured building and site outdoor description (e.g., construction products, technical equipment, land occupation, etc.)³¹. Then, the materiality service generates a material passport, which specifies the nature and quantities of the building and urban components, and links them to an EPD, which allows the calculation of LCA “midpoint” indicators (e.g., climate change, eutrophication, acidification, etc.) for the entire urban system. The data stored in the material passport are then used to calculate LCA midpoint indicators according to the RE 2020 framework (aligned with European standards) via the COMENV calculation service [157]. The LCA results are exported as a standardised file, which is integrated as input into the HIBOU service to compute the indicators related to the urban challenge “Environmental Performance” (impacts on climate change and ex-situ biodiversity). For the BAFh, the indicator related to the “in-situ biodiversity” challenge, only land use data are required (land typologies and surface area in m²).

In-situ biodiversity specificities – BAFh ontology

In the context of this project, it was decided to leverage Linked Data as the foundational framework for structuring and managing data. This approach is supported by a storage schema based on ontologies, which provide a formal, machine-readable representation of the domain’s concepts, relationships, and properties. Ontologies play a pivotal role in Linked Data by enabling semantic consistency, facilitating automated reasoning, and ensuring that data is unambiguously defined and linked across systems.

³¹ The data are structured in the form of an ontology, described in deliverable D9.4.

This choice was driven by Linked Data’s alignment with the FAIR principles, a set of guidelines ensuring that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The FAIR principles emphasise the use of persistent identifiers (Findable), standardised retrieval protocols (Accessible), shared vocabularies and metadata (Interoperable), and clear documentation and licensing (Reusable).

For the climate change and ex-situ biodiversity KPIs, which are closely linked in terms of input data, the structuring of information has been carried out through a dedicated ontology described in *Deliverable 9.4*. In contrast, the BAFh relies on a different type of data, primarily land-use categories and surface areas (m²). The unified input ontology encompasses specific aspects related to BAFh. The following section details the ontology’s components relevant to this topic.

For the BAFh needs the unified ontology provides a formalised and structured framework to represent urban surfaces and their contribution to biodiversity in cities. Unlike a simple descriptive nomenclature, an ontology makes it possible to:

- Provide a formalised and shared representation of the data by presenting concepts (project, building, road, green spaces, etc.) and their relationships;
- Associate standardised properties with each concept (surface area, type, thickness, coefficient, etc.);
- Ensure interoperability with other environmental databases across Europe (e.g., EUNIS). The database can be used beyond the French context, which is essential in a European framework;
- Manage the evolution and versioning of the BAFh nomenclature³².

The BAFh nomenclature (hierarchical across four levels, with a fixed national coefficient assigned to each type) was analysed for integration into the unified ontology. It is organised into hierarchical concepts representing the different entities being modelled (as shown in *Deliverable 9.4*, section 3.3):

- Project: carries general information (name, ID, total surface, project phase, scenarios);
- Building: includes roof surfaces and their typology (green, mineral, etc.), substrates, and vegetation layers;
- Roads: characterised by permeability, number of associated trees, and integration within the project;
- Ground-level or slab green spaces and wetlands: described by surface area, substrate thickness, vegetation layer diversity, and EUNIS correspondences.

Each entity is described by properties associated with:

- A standardised data type (string, float, integer, enum, etc.);
- A unit of measurement when relevant (e.g., m²);
- A requirement level (mandatory or optional);
- If needed, an enumeration list (enum) defining authorised values. For example:

³² the BAFh nomenclature is versioned (e.g., v2024). The ontology enables managing further updates while ensuring traceability and backward compatibility of past calculations.

- roofType: enum {mineral, green, technical}, mandatory
- projectPhase: enum {design, construction, operation}, optional
- surface: xsd:double (m²), mandatory

The BAFh nomenclature is structured into four hierarchical levels:

- Level 1: broad categories of urban surfaces (e.g., buildings, roads, green spaces);
- Level 2: sub-typologies (e.g., green roof);
- Level 3: technical details (e.g., 20 cm substrate);
- Level 4: fine-scale characteristics (e.g., number of vegetation layers).

Each BAFh land use typologies have a fixed coefficient (national value fixed by Working Group 7 of the CAP 2030 project) and a link to the EUNIS framework.

5. PERSPECTIVE OF THE METHOD

5.1. LCA practices perspectives

In addition to methodological advances and extensions such as HIBOU, major regulatory changes are currently being prepared at the European Union level, which are expected to deeply reshape the framework for life cycle-based environmental performance in the construction sector, at both construction products and building scales.

5.1.1. Construction product scale

The revised Construction Products Regulation (CPR) (EUR-Lex, 2024), adopted in April 2024 and currently in its implementation phase, aims to significantly strengthen the environmental performance disclosure requirements for construction products across the European Union. It ensures the CE marking of materials while introducing new obligations related to LCA data and EPDs.

This revision introduces the Digital Product Passports (DPPs), which will contain standardised environmental data in machine-readable formats. Initially focused on priority product categories (such as concrete, steel, insulation materials, etc.), the DPP will progressively cover a wider range of products.

Key features of the new CPR include:

- Mandatory EPDs for many product categories, with a set of minimum core environmental indicators to be declared, including GWP, resource use, water consumption, and toxicity impacts;
- Alignment with EN 15804+A2, making its modular structure and calculation methods compulsory across Europe;
- Stricter verification requirements, mandating third-party certification of LCA data to ensure reliability and consistency.

In practice, this means that all manufacturers marketing construction products in the EU will be required to provide verified LCA data according to a common framework, thereby enhancing transparency, comparability, and accessibility of environmental information across Member States. This regulatory shift is expected to support the harmonisation of LCA practices at the product level, preventing individual countries from developing diverging criteria and methodologies.

Nevertheless, some debates remain on specific implementation choices (e.g., the “worst-case scenario” approach proposed for declaring maximum environmental impacts is being questioned by several EPD program operators due to its potentially counterproductive effects).

Overall, the revised CPR is a major step towards standardising product-level environmental data in the European construction sector, facilitating cross-country comparability and promoting the integration of LCA results into Green Public Procurement (GPP) and broader sustainability strategies.

5.1.2. Building scale

The revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) [159], adopted in March 2024, marks a turning point by introducing mandatory life-cycle carbon assessment and disclosure for buildings across the European Union. This obligation will be phased in:

- From 2028 for all new public buildings above 2,000 m²;
- From 2030 for all new buildings, both public and private.

Each Member State is required to develop a national methodology to assess both embodied and operational carbon over a 50-year reference period. These methodologies must be aligned with the European standards EN 15978 (building LCA) and EN ISO 52000 series (energy performance). An EU-wide delegated act, to be published by the end of 2025, will establish a harmonised calculation framework, defining mandatory elements (included modules, 50-year time horizon, functional unit in m², etc.).

This regulatory move builds upon previous voluntary initiatives such as Level(s), the European Commission's common framework for sustainable buildings (2018–2021). Level(s) introduced a life-cycle carbon indicator and encouraged consistent application of EN 15978 across Europe. Although voluntary, Level(s) has been piloted in several countries and integrated into some national certification schemes.

In parallel, the EN 15978 standard itself is undergoing a major revision, driven by CEN/TC 350 [160]. The updated version, expected for 2026, aims to:

- Clarify the integration of Module D (benefits and loads beyond system boundaries) and circularity benefits;
- Ensure coherence with Level(s) indicators and EPBD reporting obligations;
- Address specificities of renovation projects and introduce temporal aspects (timing of emissions);
- Improve articulation with spatially-explicit approaches and digital workflows such as Building Information Modelling (BIM);
- Refine the treatment of exported energy (Modules B6/B7) and end-of-life scenarios.

These converging efforts at regulatory and standardisation levels are critical to foster a coherent, enforceable, and comparable LCA framework across the European building sector. Ultimately, the widespread adoption of EU tools (Level(s), EPBD requirements) and continuous knowledge exchange between Member States are expected to gradually reduce these inconsistencies and enhance comparability of building LCAs across Europe.

The HIBOU method, developed based on the French building LCA methodology (aligned with EN 15804 and EN 15978), will be adapted to incorporate these upcoming standard revisions.

5.2. HIBOU perspectives

The HIBOU method was designed as an integrated and adaptable framework to assess the contribution of urban projects to major environmental challenges. In the context of the WILSON project, only the carbon, ex-situ biodiversity, and in-situ biodiversity (BAFh)

indicators have been applied. Nevertheless, HIBOU is part of a broader trajectory aimed at expanding and strengthening its scope to become a European reference for multi-criteria assessment of urban development projects.

5.2.1. Broadening the scope of application

HIBOU is based on a modular methodological architecture, which allows for the progressive integration of new challenges beyond those addressed in this project. The next steps notably include:

- Water management: integration of indicators for hydrological regulation (infiltration, runoff, evapotranspiration) which are essential in the context of climate change and increasing flood risks;
- Social and economic dimensions: exploration of links with property value, social acceptability of urban projects, and the reduction of inequalities in access to nature.

This expansion will enable HIBOU to establish itself as a systemic method, capable of connecting the multiple dimensions of urban sustainability.

5.2.2. Scientific consolidation and European harmonisation

To ensure the robustness and legitimacy of its results, the HIBOU method relies on scientific research and ongoing validation. Future directions include:

- Improving underlying models: refining indicators to better capture the specific pressures of urban environments;
- Harmonisation with regulatory frameworks: HIBOU will be continuously updated to integrate developments from the revised CPR and EPBD, two regulatory pillars redefining environmental requirements in the building sector;
- Validation through practice: implementation of the method across a panel of pilot projects, particularly in Europe (see Deliverable D12.2 - 2026), to test and adjust indicators in diverse contexts.

These efforts aim to position HIBOU as a scientifically robust and institutionally recognised method at the European level.

5.2.3. Strengthening operationalisation and adoption

One of the distinctive features of HIBOU is its ambition to be directly usable by operational stakeholders (local authorities, developers, engineering firms, researchers). Future directions in this regard include:

- Development of dedicated digital tools: user-friendly web interfaces to calculate HIBOU indicators from project data, compare multiple planning scenarios, and monitor results over time;
- Integration into existing digital ecosystems: ensuring compatibility with BIM environments, urban GIS systems, and building/neighbourhood LCA platforms (e.g., UrbanPrint);
- Training and dissemination: creation of pedagogical resources, methodological guides, and training programs to support practitioners in using the method;

- Adoption by public policies: collaboration with national and local authorities to position HIBOU as a reference tool in sustainable urban planning processes and environmental certification schemes.

Ultimately, the goal is for HIBOU to become a standard decision-support tool, ensuring that every project effectively contributes to sustainability objectives.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable set out to explore how digital twins can support life-cycle data solutions for non-energy uses, with a particular focus on carbon and biodiversity issues. Throughout the work, two main challenges have emerged:

- The availability and collection of input data specific to non-energy aspects, which differs from traditional energy-related assessments;
- The need for a robust and efficient methodology to assess environmental performance, both in terms of carbon and biodiversity, at multiple scales.

To address these challenges, the deliverable examined current LCA practices across Europe, introduced an integrated assessment framework (HIBOU), and reflected on future perspectives for harmonisation and operational implementation.

Section 3 addressed these challenges by providing a detailed review of current LCA practices across 14 European countries. This review was conducted at the product, building, and district scales, offering insight into both regulatory and voluntary approaches. The analysis showed that, although full harmonisation is still lacking, several countries (6 out of 14) have already embedded LCA into their building regulations. This benchmarking exercise supports the identification of good practices and helps strike a balance between data-gathering effort and the added value of robust results. While collecting detailed data can be demanding, it is essential for accurate modelling. National frameworks and databases can play a key role in easing data access and standardisation, especially where regulations exist.

Section 4 introduced the HIBOU methodology, developed to respond to one of the key gaps identified in conventional LCA: the lack of biodiversity-related indicators. Indeed, the scientific consensus is clear: to effectively address global challenges, climate change and biodiversity must be tackled jointly. Traditional LCA mainly valorises carbon impacts and neglects the positive contributions of green infrastructure. In response, HIBOU proposes an integrated assessment framework, with indicators that capture both environmental impacts (e.g., climate change, land use, pollution) and ecological benefits (e.g., biodiversity support, cooling effects, water regulation). In the specific context of the WILSON project, only one ecosystem service covered by HIBOU is currently addressed: the service of biodiversity support. By combining carbon and biodiversity metrics (in-situ and ex-situ), HIBOU provides a systemic perspective aligned with the ambition for ecological neutrality in built environments. The WILSON project has led to the development of calculation models capable to assess a set of eight indicators covering both climate change and biodiversity-related pressures :

- Global Warming Potential (GWP, kg CO₂eq/m²)
- Global Warming for Terrestrial Ecosystems (GWTE, PDF.m².year)
- Global Warming for Freshwater Ecosystems (GWFE, PDF.m².year)
- Terrestrial Acidification (TA, PDF.m².year)
- Freshwater Eutrophication (FWE, PDF.m².year)
- Water Consumption for Terrestrial Ecosystems (WCTE, PDF.m².year)
- Water Consumption for Aquatic Ecosystems (WCAE, PDF.m².year)
- Harmonised Biotope Area Factor (BAFh)

Together, these indicators provide an integrated perspective on the potential impacts of urban development projects on climate and biodiversity.

Section 5 looked ahead to future developments. It first reflected on the evolving European regulatory context, including revisions of the CPR and the EPBD, which are pushing for more harmonised and comprehensive LCA practices. It then outlined the future developments of the HIBOU methodology, notably its deployment in pilot cases at the European scale. Implementation on the pilot site is planned under Task 12.2, with results to be delivered in the Deliverable 12.2 (scheduled for October 2026). These experiments will be a decisive step to test, refine, and validate the operational relevance of the approach.

In summary, this deliverable lays the groundwork for a much-needed convergence between carbon and biodiversity assessment and opens the way for a more systematic integration of these dimensions into planning and regulatory tools. The upcoming work will help consolidate these achievements and demonstrate, through experimentation, the added value of the proposed solutions in supporting the ecological transition of European territories.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] AFNOR, “NF EN ISO 14040 – Management environnemental – Analyse du cycle de vie – Principes et cadre,” 2006.
- [2] AFNOR, “NF EN ISO 14044 – Management environnemental – Analyse du cycle de vie – Exigences et lignes directrices,” 2006.
- [3] AFNOR, “NF EN 15804 – Contribution des ouvrages de construction au développement durable – Déclarations environnementales sur les produits – Règles régissant les catégories de produits de construction,” 2016.
- [4] AFNOR, “NF EN 15978 – Contribution des ouvrages de construction au développement durable – Évaluation de la performance environnementale des bâtiments – Méthode de calcul,” 2012.
- [5] European Commission, “Level(s) European framework for sustainable buildings,” https://green-forum.ec.europa.eu/levels_en.
- [6] European Commission, “European Platform on LCA | EPLCA,” <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/EnvironmentalFootprint.html>.
- [7] ECOINVENT, “Ecoinvent 3.” Accessed: Jun. 12, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ecoinvent.org/home.html>
- [8] E. Fraile-Garcia, J. Ferreiro-Cabello, E. Martinez-Camara, and E. Jimenez-Macias, “Adaptation of methodology to select structural alternatives of one-way slab in residential building to the guidelines of the European Committee for Standardization (CEN/TC 350),” *Environ Impact Assess Rev*, vol. 55, pp. 144–155, Nov. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.eiar.2015.08.004.
- [9] N. Ata-Ali, V. Penadés-Plà, D. Martínez-Muñoz, and V. Yepes, “Recycled versus non-recycled insulation alternatives: LCA analysis for different climatic conditions in Spain,” *Resour Conserv Recycl*, vol. 175, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105838.
- [10] ITeC, “BEDEC,” 2024. Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://metabase.itec.cat/vidoe/es/bedec/itec>
- [11] ECO-PLATFORM, “Eco-Portal.”
- [12] CATEB, “ENVIRONMENTAL LABEL – DAPcons® THE SYSTEM TO DECLARE THE ENVIRONMENTAL COMMITMENT OF YOUR PRODUCTS.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cateb.cat/dapconstruccion-programme/>
- [13] ECO-PLATFORM, “ECO EPD PROGRAMMES,” 2025, Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eco-platform.org/the-eco-epd-programs.html>
- [14] BREEAM, “BREEAM®. La certification des bâtiments durables.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://breeam.es/>
- [15] U.S. Green Building Council, “LEED v5 | U.S. Green Building Council.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.usgbc.org/leed/v5>
- [16] Greendesignconsulting, “LEED en Chiffres: Etat des lieux des projets.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://fr.greendesignconsulting.com/single-post/leed-en-chiffres-etat-des-lieux-des-projets>
- [17] GBCE, “Methodology – VERDE.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://gbce.es/metodologia-verde/>
- [18] GBCE, “Green Building Council Spain – Conseil pour la construction durable en Espagne est la principale organisation de construction durable de notre pays,.” 2025. Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://gbce.es/>

- [19] NETZEROCITIES, “Spain’s Pilot Activity: URBANEW: Multi-stakeholder innovative and systemic solutions for urban regeneration Spain – NetZeroCities,” 2023. Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://netzerocities.eu/spains-pilot-activity-multi-stakeholder-innovative-and-systemic-solutions-for-urban-regeneration-spain/>
- [20] J. M. Alonso and L. Sitges, “Spanish Public Law in 2021: 10 Things to Look Out For,” *Global Environment, Land & Resources Blog*. Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.globalelr.com/2021/02/spanish-public-law-in-2021-10-things-to-look-out-for/>
- [21] M. del P. Pablo-Romero, A. Sánchez-Braza, and C. Torreblanca, “Implementing the Circular Economy in the European Union and Spain: Links to the Low-Carbon Transition,” *Energies* 2024, Vol. 17, Page 5255, vol. 17, no. 21, p. 5255, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.3390/EN17215255.
- [22] SIMAPRO, “SimaPro - Sustainability insights for informed changemakers.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://simapro.com/?google-ads&utm_term=life%20cycle%20assessment%20software&utm_campaign=SimaPro%20-%20Benelux&utm_source=adwords&utm_medium=ppc&hsa_acc=1527573210&hsa_cam=198667581&hsa_grp=11258980581&hsa_ad=497962322150&hsa_src=g&hsa_tgt=kwd-313690707539&hsa_kw=life%20cycle%20assessment%20software&hsa_mt=b&hsa_net=adwords&hsa_ver=3&gad_source=1&gad_campaignid=198667581&gbraid=0AAAAAD_tK8cv4A2CZ2kExIz_1UU2Tyv4E&gclid=Cj0KCQjwyvFDBhDYARIsAltbZEGmWTGMypIIFOCQ7ncQxnzoke0IUmGJAUryF8xb0DV6Yf7tGDyUYUaAhq7EALw_wcB
- [23] OneClickLCA, “Logiciel ACV & DEP pour la construction et la fabrication.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://oneclicklca.com/fr/>
- [24] OpenLCA, “OpenLCA.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.openlca.org/>
- [25] OneClickLCA, “Espagne : Bâtiments VERDE 2020/2022 : Analyse du cycle de vie et durabilité | One Click LCA.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://help.oneclicklca.com/en/articles/275717-espana-verde-edificios-2020-2022-analisis-de-ciclo-de-vida-y-sostenibilidad>
- [26] Ministère de l’aménagement du territoire et de la décentralisation and de la B. Ministère de la Transition écologique, “Réglementation environnementale RE2020 | Ministères Aménagement du territoire Transition écologique.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/politiques-publiques/reglementation-environnementale-re2020>
- [27] PEP ecopassport, “PEP ecopassport®.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://www.pep-ecopassport.org/fr/>
- [28] INIES, “Inies, les données environnementales et sanitaires de référence pour le bâtiment et la RE2020 - Inies.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.inies.fr/>
- [29] Brightway, “Brightway LCA Software Framework — Brightway documentation.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.brightway.dev/en/latest/>
- [30] MTE and Cerema, “Guide RE2020 - Eco-construire pour le confort de tous,” 2024. Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available:

- https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/documents/guide_re2020_version_janvier_2024.pdf
- [31] CYPE, “ELODIE by CYPE – CYPE.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://info.cype.com/fr/software/elodie-by-cype/>
- [32] Perrenoud, “LES LOGICIELS RE2020 disponibles – Logiciels Perrenoud.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://logicielsperrenoud.com/2021/07/17/les-logiciels-re2020-disponibles/>
- [33] Nooco, “Logiciel ACV et RE2020 – Nooco.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nooco.com/>
- [34] IZUBA énergies, “Logiciel Pleiades ACV – Analyse du cycle de vie de votre bâtiment.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.izuba.fr/logiciels/outils-logiciels/re-2020-acv/>
- [35] RE-BATIMENT, “OPEE (V. 1.7.3).” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://re-batiment2020.cstb.fr/opee/>
- [36] ADEME, “Méthode Quartier Energie Carbone,” 2022. Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://bibliothèque.ademe.fr/batiment/5802-methode-quartier-energie-carbone.html>
- [37] Efficacity, “UrbanPrint.” Accessed: Jul. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://efficacity.com/urbanprint/>
- [38] CEREMA, “L’ACV DYNAMIQUE DANS LA RE 2020,” 2022.
- [39] WORLD GREEN BUILDING COUNCIL, “How life cycle GWP measures are being implemented by governments – Measures taken in Denmark, France, Sweden and London,” 2024. Accessed: Aug. 03, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://worldgbc.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/WorldGBC-case-studies-report-GWP.pdf>
- [40] Nationale MILIEUDATABASE, “Environmental Performance.” Accessed: Jul. 22, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://milieudatabase.nl/en/environmental-performance/>
- [41] Nationale MILIEUDATABASE, “Dutch Environmental Database.” Accessed: Jul. 22, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://milieudatabase.nl/en/database/dutch-environmental-database/>
- [42] Nationale MILIEUDATABASE, “Viewer.” Accessed: Jul. 22, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://milieudatabase.nl/nl/viewer/>
- [43] MRPI, “Milieu Relevante Product Informatie.” Accessed: Jul. 22, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mrpi.nl/>
- [44] Nationale MILIEUDATABASE, “Bepalingsmethode Milieuprestatie Bouwwerken,” 2023. [Online]. Available: www.nieman.nl
- [45] D. Straeten, “A review and evaluation of the Dutch MPG approach for building sustainability assessment A Cube Homes case study,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tue.nl/en/our-university/about-the-university/organization/integrity/scientific-integrity/>
- [46] Nationale MILIEUDATABASE, “Calculation tools.” Accessed: Jul. 22, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://milieudatabase.nl/en/environmental-performance/calculation-tools/>
- [47] BIMPACT, “Bouwwerken toetsen op MPG wordt een fluitje van een cent – BIMPACT.” Accessed: Jul. 22, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bimpact.nl/toetshulpen/mpg-toetshulp/>

- [48] MRPI, “MPG Master - Calculator.” Accessed: Jul. 22, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mrpi.nl/mpg-master/>
- [49] GPR, “Logiciel GPR.” Accessed: Jul. 22, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://gprsoftware.nl/>
- [50] NIEMAN, “DEMARCATIE MILIEUPRESTATIE IN BOUWREGELGEVING – MINISTERIE VAN BZK,” 2023. [Online]. Available: www.nieman.nl
- [51] Circle Economy, TNO, and FABRIC, “CIRCULAR AMSTERDAM : A vision and action agenda for the city and metropolitan area,” 2016.
- [52] City deal, “City Deal Circulair en Conceptueel Bouwen.” Accessed: Jul. 22, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://citydealccb.nl/>
- [53] Green Building Council Italia, “L’Italia unico Paese europeo nella Top 10 delle certificazioni LEED® di USGBC.” Accessed: Sep. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://gbcitalia.org/2025/02/14/litalia-unico-paese-europeo-nella-top-10-delle-certificazioni-leed-di-usgbc/>
- [54] J. Famiglietti, H. A. Toosi, A. Dénarié, and M. Motta, “Developing a new data-driven LCA tool at the urban scale: The case of the energy performance of the building sector,” *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 256, p. 115389, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2022.115389.
- [55] L. Di Pilla *et al.*, “Fostering the energy transition in a neighbourhood perspective: towards Positive Energy Districts’ application for a university case study,” *Energy Reports*, vol. 13, pp. 5628–5652, Jun. 2025, doi: 10.1016/J.EGYR.2025.05.012.
- [56] E. Palumbo, M. Traverso, E. Antonini, and A. Boeri, “Towards a sustainable district: a streamlined Life cycle assessment applied to an Italian urban district,” *IOP Conf Ser Earth Environ Sci*, vol. 323, no. 1, p. 012095, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/323/1/012095.
- [57] PANGPP, “CRITERI AMBIENTALI MINIMI PER L’AFFIDAMENTO DEL SERVIZIO DI PROGETTAZIONE ED ESECUZIONE DEI LAVORI DI INTERVENTI EDILIZI,” 2024. Accessed: Sep. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://gpp.mase.gov.it/sites/default/files/2024-08/allegato-tecnico-CAM-edilizia-07-06-2022-rev-correttivo.pdf>
- [58] Green Building Council Italia, “Strumenti per la decarbonizzazione nella sfida della transizione ecologica dell’ambiente costruito.” Accessed: Sep. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://gbcitalia.org/2025/06/25/strumenti-per-la-decarbonizzazione-nella-sfida-della-transizione-ecologica-dellambiente-costruito/>
- [59] EUROPEAN COMMISSION, “Sustainable Construction in Public and Private Works through IPP approach.” Accessed: Jul. 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/project/LIFE05-ENV-GR-000235/sustainable-construction-in-public-and-private-works-through-ipp-approach>
- [60] V. S. Orfanidou, N. P. Rachaniotis, G. T. Tsoulfas, and G. P. Chondrokoukis, “Life Cycle Costing Implementation in Green Public Procurement: A Case Study from the Greek Public Sector,” *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 15, no. 3, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.3390/su15032817.
- [61] SIDENOR, “Sidenor is the first steel producer in Greece awarded with the Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) • Sidenor.” Accessed: Jul. 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://sidenor.gr/en/sidenor-is-the-first-steel-producer-in-greece-awarded-with-the-environmental-product-declaration-epd/>

- [62] INTERMIX, “Περιβαλλοντικές Δηλώσεις Προϊόντων (EPD).” Accessed: Jul. 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://intermix.gr/en/viosimi-anaptyksi/perivallon/epd/>
- [63] KEBE, “ENVIRONMENTAL PRODUCT DECLARATION – EPD FOR KEBE | KEBE.” Accessed: Jul. 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kebe-sa.gr/en/new/environmental-product-declaration-epd-for-kebe/>
- [64] P. Chastas, T. Theodosiou, K. J. Kontoleon, and D. Bikas, “The effect of embodied impact on the cost-optimal levels of nearly zero energy buildings: A case study of a residential building in Thessaloniki, Greece,” *Energies (Basel)*, vol. 10, no. 6, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.3390/en10060740.
- [65] M. Ormazabal, C. Jaca, and R. Puga-Leal, “Analysis and comparison of life cycle assessment and carbon footprint software,” in *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, Springer Verlag, 2014, pp. 1521–1530. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-55122-2_131.
- [66] O.-M. L. Georgakopoulou, D. Kaliampakos, K. Koutsopoulos, and C. Koronaios, “Matériaux isolants et durabilité dans la construction moderne. Évaluation environnementale du polystyrène expansé et du xynomalos.” Accessed: Jul. 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://www.openarchives.gr/aggregator-openarchives/edm/ntua/000011-123456789_5204
- [67] KERKYRA Publications, “LEED certification in Greece: Athens leads.” Accessed: Jul. 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ekdoseiskerkyra.gr/en/leed-certification-in-greece-athens-leads-thessaloniki-follows/>
- [68] J. DE BURCA, “Greece Green Building History.” Accessed: Jul. 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://constructive-voices.com/greece-green-building-history/>
- [69] ÖKOBAUDAT, “Système d’évaluation pour la construction durable (BNB) .” Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oekobaudat.de/en/home/assessment-system-for-sustainable-building-bnb.html>
- [70] DGNB, “DGNB System for New Construction ,” 2023. Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dgnb.de/en/certification/buildings/new-construction>
- [71] IBU, “Published EPDs.” Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://ibu-epd.com/en/published-epds/>
- [72] ÖKOBAUDAT, “Database ÖKOBAUDAT.” Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://www.oekobaudat.de/no_cache/en/database/search/daten/db3.html#bereich3
- [73] WECOBIS, “Ökologisches Baustoffinformationssystem.” Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.wecobis.de/>
- [74] Vizcab, “Embodied carbon in Germany: a state-of-play.” Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://blog.vizcab.io/en/international-blog/embodied-carbon-in-germany-a-state-of-play>
- [75] U. A. and S. D. Ferderal Institute for Research on Buiding, “eLCA.” Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bauteileditor.de/>
- [76] DGNB, “DGNB Certification: Urban districts.” Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dgnb.de/en/certification/important-facts-about-dgnb-certification/certification-schemes/urban-districts>
- [77] DGNB, “Life Level(s).” Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dgnb.de/en/dgnb/dgnb-initiatives-and-projects/translate-to-english-life-levels>

- [78] Environdec, “EPD International System.” Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.environdec.com/home>
- [79] Peikko Group, “Environmental Product Declaration, EPD.” Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.peikko.com/sustainability/environment-and-quality/epd/>
- [80] Vestaconsulting, “Sustainable buildings .” Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.vestaconsulting.lt/en/services/sustainable-buildings/>
- [81] InterregEurope, “Lithuanian Building Sustainability Assessment System.” Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/lithuanian-building-sustainability-assessment-system>
- [82] V. Chandrasekaran, J. Dvarioniene, A. Vitkute, and G. Gecevicius, “Environmental impact assessment of renovated multi-apartment building using LCA approach: Case study from Lithuania,” *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1–18, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.3390/su13031542.
- [83] Kaunas University of Technology, “LCA4Regions - Interreg Europe - ACTION PLAN - Lithuania,” 2022. Accessed: Jul. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: www.interregeurope.eu/lca4regions
- [84] EPD Turkey, “EPD Türkiye.” Accessed: Jul. 26, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.epdturkey.org/>
- [85] SURATAM, “Sustainable Product Certificates.” Accessed: Jul. 26, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.suratam.com/en/our-services/sustainable-product-certificates/>
- [86] SURATAM, “Databases.” Accessed: Jul. 26, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.suratam.com/en/our-services/databases/>
- [87] İ. Kutlu and İ. Bekar, “Investigation of building certification systems in terms of sustainable preservation: the case of Mardin city in Turkey,” *Mehran University Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, vol. 42, no. 1, p. 183, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.22581/muet1982.2301.17.
- [88] Construction 21, “Turkish Green Building Council (ÇEDBİK).” Accessed: Jul. 26, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.construction21.org/company/h/turkish-green-building-council-cedbk.html>
- [89] Concrete Sustainability Council, “The Turkish Green Building Council recognizes the CSC Certification in the B.E.S.T. .” Accessed: Jul. 26, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://csc.eco/2023/05/19/the-turkish-green-building-council-recognizes-the-csc-certification-in-the-b-e-s-t/>
- [90] M. C. , K. E. B. , K. Y. , A. S. M. , G. F. B. , G. M. T. , & Ü. B. B. Mercan, “Overall approach to building LCA and recent studies in Türkiye,” *Advances in Building Energy Research*, 2024.
- [91] N. C. Kayaçetin, “A Life cycle assessment based decision support tool for early-design phase of mass-housing neighbourhoods in Turkey,” 2018, Accessed: Jul. 26, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://open.metu.edu.tr/handle/11511/27766>
- [92] ECOINVENT Support, “Building and Construction.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://support.ecoinvent.org/building-and-construction>
- [93] SUGB, “Umweltproduktedeklaration (EPD).” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sugb.ch/dienstleistungen/umweltproduktedeklaration-epd/>

- [94] KBOB, “Données écobilans dans la construction.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kbob.admin.ch/fr/donnees-ecobilans-dans-la-construction>
- [95] Minergie, “ECO Certification.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.minergie.ch/fr/certification/eco/>
- [96] SNBS, “SNBS.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.snbs-hochbau.ch/>
- [97] SIA, “SIA 2032 / 2020 F - L'énergie grise - Établissement du bilan écologique pour la construction de bâtiments (Collection des normes => Architecte)».” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://shop.sia.ch/normenwerk/architekt/2032_2020_f/F/Product/
- [98] Minergie, “Minergie-Quartier Certification.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.minergie.ch/fr/certification/minergie-quartier/>
- [99] A. Naneva, M. Bonanomi, A. Hollberg, G. Habert, and D. Hall, “Integrated BIM-Based LCA for the Entire Building Process Using an Existing Structure for Cost Estimation in the Swiss Context,” *Sustainability 2020, Vol. 12, Page 3748*, vol. 12, no. 9, p. 3748, May 2020, doi: 10.3390/SU12093748.
- [100] BRE, “Environmental Product Declarations for construction products with BRE.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://bregroup.com/insights/environmental-product-declarations-for-construction-products-with-bre>
- [101] GreenHouse Protocol, “Bath Inventory of Carbon and Energy (ICE).” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://ghgprotocol.org/Third-Party-Databases/Bath-ICE>
- [102] BREEAM, “Sustainable Building Certification.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://breeam.com/>
- [103] LETI, “Climate Emergency Design Guide.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.leti.uk/cedg>
- [104] RICS, “Whole life carbon assessment for the built environment RICS PROFESSIONAL STANDARD,” 2024, Accessed: Aug. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: www.rics.org
- [105] UKGBC, “Embodied Carbon Modelling and Reporting.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://ukgbc.org/resources/embodied-carbon-modelling-and-reporting/>
- [106] CATAPULT, “UK Cities Climate Investment Commission.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://cp.catapult.org.uk/project/uk-cities-climate-investment-commission/>
- [107] One Click LCA, “Part Z: Whole-life carbon shaping UK construction .” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://oneclicklca.com/en/resources/articles/part-z-whole-life-carbon-rules-for-uk-construction>
- [108] One Click LCA, “EMBODIED CARBON BENCHMARKS FOR EUROPEAN BUILDINGS,” 2021.
- [109] RIBA, “RIBA 2030 Climate Challenge - Version 2,” 2021.
- [110] EPD Norge, “EPD-Norge Digi .” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.epd-norge.no/digi/>
- [111] EDP-Norge, “Process Data set: Leca® Letklinker 10-20; Hinge (en).” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://epdnorway.lca-data.com/datasetdetail/process.xhtml?uuid=06f4050b-cb0c-4920-978f-9d588f8ce12c&version=00.08.000&stock=InData_2018&lang=en

- [112] Byggtjeneste, “Alle produkter i Byggtjeneste.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://byggtjeneste.no/alle-produkter-i-byggtjeneste/>
- [113] EPD Norge, “PCR register .” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.epd-norge.no/pcr/epd-norges-pcr-register/>
- [114] OneClickLCA, “Norsk Byggtjeneste and One Click LCA enters a partnership.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://oneclicklca.com/en/resources/press-release/norsk-byggtjeneste-partners-up-with-one-click-lca-to-boost-epd-adoption-in-norway>
- [115] M. K. Wiik *et al.*, “GHG emission requirements and benchmark values in Norwegian building codes,” *588*, vol. 588, no. 2, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/588/2/022005.
- [116] M. K. Wiik, S. Homaei, rekling Lien Synne, and I. Sartori, *ZERO EMISSION NEIGHBOURHOODS IN SMART CITIES Definition, assessment criteria and key performance indicators Version 5.0. English*. 2024. [Online]. Available: www.ntnu.no
- [117] ARV, “Oslo, Norway.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://greendeal-arv.eu/2022/02/07/norway/>
- [118] Nordic Sustainable Construction, “Buildings’ Life Cycle Assessments gain ground in the Nordics | Nordic Sustainable Construction.” Accessed: Jul. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nordicsustainableconstruction.com/news/2023/january/denmark-introduces-co2-limit-for-new-constructions>
- [119] EDP Danmark, “EPD Databasen.” Accessed: Jul. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.epddanmark.dk/epd-databasen/>
- [120] LCAByg, “Publications – Abstract of the BUILD REPORT 2021 : 25.” Accessed: Jul. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.lcabyg.dk/en/publications/>
- [121] M. Balouktsi and H. Birgisdottir, “Analysis of new modules in connection with calculation of the climate impact of buildings,” 2023. Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://vbn.aau.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/611627474/2023_23_Climate_impact_from_new_modules.pdf
- [122] LCAByg, “About LCAByg.” Accessed: Jul. 29, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://lcabyg.dk/en/about-lcabyg/>
- [123] J. Kragh, J. Rose, and S. Aggerholm, “Cost-optimal levels of minimum energy performance requirements in the Danish Building Regulations (3),” 2023. Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://vbn.aau.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/553979646/Cost-optimal_levels_of_minimum_energy_performance_requirements_in_the_Danish_Building_Regulations_3.pdf
- [124] Nordic Sustainable Construction, “Buildings’ Life Cycle Assessments gain ground in the Nordic.” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nordicsustainableconstruction.com/news/2023/january/denmark-introduces-co2-limit-for-new-constructions>
- [125] Nordregio, “Sustainability Certification of Neighbourhoods: Experience from DGNB New Urban Districts in Denmark.” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://archive.nordregio.se/en/Metameny/Nordregio-News/2014/Planning-Tools-for-Urban-Sustainability/Case/index.html>

- [126] EG, “EG presents BIM and sustainability at Building Green 2023.” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://egsoftware.com/global/ressource/eg-presents-bim-and-sustainability-at-building-green-2023>
- [127] EG, “Mandatory new requirements for sustainable construction.” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://egsoftware.com/global/ressource/mandatory-new-requirements-for-sustainable-construction>
- [128] Nordic Sustainable Construction, “Nordic Harmonisation of Life Cycle Assessment (2021-2024).” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nordicsustainableconstruction.com/work-packages/nordic-harmonisation-of-life-cycle-assessment>
- [129] Nordic Sustainable Construction, “The Nordics Aim to be Leading in Sustainable Construction.” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nordicsustainableconstruction.com/news/2024/august/meeting-with-the-nordic-ministers>
- [130] EPD International, “EPD International AB .” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.environdec.com/about-us/epd-international-ab>
- [131] Boverkets klimatdatabas, “Boverkets klimatdatabas.” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://klimatdatabasen.boverket.se/>
- [132] Boverket, “Climate database from Boverket .” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.boverket.se/en/start/laws-and-regulations/climate-declaration/climate-database>
- [133] IVL, “The construction sector’s actions for the climate.” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ivl.se/english/ivl/about-ivl/research-and-development/the-societal-benefits-of-research/the-construction-sectors-actions-for-the-climate.html>
- [134] Boverket, “Climate declaration for new buildings.” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.boverket.se/en/start/laws-and-regulations/climate-declaration/>
- [135] Boverket, “Climate declaration follow-up and statistics.” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.boverket.se/en/start/laws-and-regulations/climate-declaration/statistics>
- [136] O. Nils, “LCA of Low-temperature District Heating Network Components | Lunds universitet,” 2021. Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.lu.se/lup/publication/9038080>
- [137] M. Fröling and M. Svanström, “Life cycle assessment of the district heat distribution system. Part 2: Network construction,” *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 425–435, Nov. 2005, doi: 10.1065/LCA2004.12.195.
- [138] H. Wallbaum and H. Baumann, “Integration of LCa in the planning, design and construction of residential buildings.” Accessed: Aug. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://research.chalmers.se/en/project/8994>
- [139] Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment, “Low-carbon roadmaps .” Accessed: Aug. 03, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://tem.fi/en/low-carbon-roadmaps-2035>
- [140] SKYPE, “CO2DATA - Emissions database for construction.” Accessed: Aug. 03, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://co2data.fi/#en>

- [141] Metsä Wood, “Producer and seller of premium quality Kerto® LVL, plywood and other wood products.” Accessed: Aug. 03, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.metsagroup.com/metsawood/>
- [142] T. Rätty and M. Jallinoja, “EPD of Finnish sawn and planed timber,” 2021, *The Building Information Foundation RTS sr*. Accessed: Aug. 03, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://jukuri.luke.fi/handle/11111/5888>
- [143] Ministry of the Environment, “Environmental impact assessment.” Accessed: Aug. 03, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ymparisto.fi/en/civic-activity/environmental-impact-assessment>
- [144] Sparcs, “Reykjavík and Lahti Collaborate in NetZeroCitiesEU Initiative.” Accessed: Aug. 03, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://sparcs.info/en/news/reykjavik-and-lahti-collaborate-in-netzerocitieseu-initiative>
- [145] Stardust, “It’s time to replicate with Tampere .” Accessed: Aug. 03, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://stardustproject.eu/news/its-time-to-replicate-with-tampere>
- [146] RAMBOLL, “Which life cycle assessment? Managing the risk of inconsistent building assessments across regions.” Accessed: Jul. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ramboll.com/en-us/insights/decarbonise-for-net-zero/which-life-cycle-assessment>
- [147] C. Ayik, H. Ayatac, and B. Sertyesilisik, “A Gap Analysis on Urban Sustainability Studies and Urban Sustainability Assessment Tools,” *Architecture Research*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–15, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.5923/J.ARCH.20170701.01.
- [148] H. Kaur and P. Garg, “Urban sustainability assessment tools: A review,” *J Clean Prod*, vol. 210, pp. 146–158, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2018.11.009.
- [149] OID, “Barometre 2021 de l’immobilier responsable,” 2021.
- [150] MTE, “Le bâtiment, un secteur clef pour la préservation et la reconquête de la biodiversité. Résultat d’enquête,” 2021.
- [151] IPCC and IPBES, “BIODIVERSITY AND CLIMATE CHANGE,” 2021. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4782538.
- [152] CSTB, “CSTB Presents HIBOU Method at EGU25 .” Accessed: Sep. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://wilson-project.eu/events-and-news/cstb-presents-hibou-method-at-egu25/>
- [153] T. Koellner *et al.*, “UNEP-SETAC guideline on global land use impact assessment on biodiversity and ecosystem services in LCA,” *Int J Life Cycle Assess*, vol. 18, pp. 1188–1202, 2013, doi: 10.1007/s11367-013-0579-z.
- [154] R. Seed, “Product Biodiversity Footprint – A novel approach to compare the impact of products on biodiversity combining Life Cycle Assessment and Ecology,” *Setac europe*, pp. 224–224, 2008.
- [155] A. Brachet, M. Olmos, N. Schiopu, and P. Clergeau, “Relevance of considering LCA and ecological expertise methods to evaluate biodiversity impact of green roofs,” in *SETAC Europe 29 th Annual Meeting – Abstract book*, 2019.
- [156] CEN, “CEN/TC 350 Evaluation of the possibility of adding environmental impact categories and related indicators and calculation methods for the assessment of the environmental performance of buildings pour avis.” AFNOR, 2016.
- [157] CSTB, “COMENV – Le moteur de calcul pour la simulation environnementale des bâtiments,” 2020. Accessed: Sep. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available:

<https://www.cstb.fr/getmedia/8df54fa8-fffb-4c9c-b124-33d55d8233eb/CSTB-moteur-calcul-comenv.pdf>

- [158] EUR-Lex, “Regulation (EU) 2024/3110 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2024 laying down harmonised rules for the marketing of construction products and repealing Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 (Text with EEA relevance).” Accessed: Aug. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/3110/oj/eng>
- [159] EUR-Lex, “Directive (EU) 2024/1275 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 April 2024 on the energy performance of buildings (recast) (Text with EEA relevance).” Accessed: Aug. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2024/1275/oj/eng>
- [160] CEN/TC 350, “CEN/TC 350 - Sustainability of construction works - FprEN 15978.” Accessed: Aug. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:110:0:::FSP_PROJECT,FSP_LANG_ID:78444,25&cs=1C000B7CCACDFE8965F11BC37FCEF569C

8. ANNEX

8.1. Annex 1: Models to convert LCA midpoint indicators to HIBOU LCA endpoint indicators (2020 version)

Figure 7: Conversion of LCA midpoint indicators into biodiversity endpoint impacts using the HIBOU method.

Linear regression models → LCA Endpoint Indicators = $a \times$ LCA Midpoint indicators + b

- Global warming Terrestrial ecosystems = $1,98E-01 \times$ Global_Warming + $2,00E-03$
- Global warming Freshwater ecosystems = $1,00E-04 \times$ Global_Warming + $1,24E-06$
- Terrestrial acidification = $1,20E+01 \times$ Acidification for soil and water - $1,80E-03$
- Freshwater Eutrophisation = $2,68E+02 \times$ Eutrophisation - $2,51E-01$
- Water consumption Terrestrial ecosystem = $9,29E-01 \times$ Net use of fresh water + $4,77E-05$
- Water consumption Aquatic ecosystem = $8,00E-04 \times$ Net use of fresh water + $4,01E-08$

8.2. Annex 2: BAFh nomenclature

8.2.1. Buildings category

Category		Biodiversity hosting capacity coefficient	Description / Conditions	Calculation rule
Conventional roofs		0	Gravel, metal, tile, asphalt roof, etc.	
Green roofs	<i>Extensive - (< 8 cm substrate)</i>	Single plant stratum: sedums	0.1*	The proposed thicknesses correspond to substrate thickness only, excluding drainage layer. Sedums are succulent plants with shallow root systems. Herbaceous plants are non-woody plants with generally short life cycles (grasses, clovers, asters, etc.). Shrubs are woody plants less than 7 m high (lavender, rosemary, honeysuckle, hornbeam, sage, hawthorn, etc.). Trees are woody plants over 7 m high (maples, linden, plane trees, chestnut, pagoda trees, etc.).
	<i>Extensive + (9-12 cm substrate)</i>	Single plant stratum: herbaceous	0.2	
		Combination of 2 plant strata: herbaceous + shrubs	0.3	
	<i>Semi-intensive (13-30 cm substrate)</i>	Single plant stratum: herbaceous or shrubs	0.3	
		Combination of 2 plant strata: herbaceous + shrubs	0.4	
	<i>Intensive - (31-60 cm substrate)</i>	Single plant stratum: herbaceous or shrubs or trees	0.4	
		Combination of 2 plant strata: herbaceous + shrubs, or herbaceous + trees, or shrubs + trees	0.5	
		Combination of 3 plant strata: herbaceous + shrubs + trees	0.6	
	<i>Intensive + (> 60 cm substrate)</i>	Single plant stratum: herbaceous or shrubs or trees	0.5	
		Combination of 2 plant strata: herbaceous + shrubs, or herbaceous + trees, or shrubs + trees	0.6	
Combination of 3 plant strata: herbaceous + shrubs + trees		0.7		

8.2.2. Roads category

Category	Biodiversity hosting capacity coefficient	Description / Conditions	Calculation rule
Impermeable mineral surfaces	0*	Fully sealed surfaces with air and/or water impermeable coverings that prevent vegetation growth: concrete, asphalt, terrazzo, ceramic, slabs/paving (with substructure or jointing), waterproof plastic coatings, bitumen, slabs with mortar base. Impermeable wastelands fall into this category.	
Semi-permeable and permeable mineral surfaces	0.1	Materials partially or fully permeable to air and water but preventing vegetation growth: large and small stone pavers, clinker, wooden paving, composite concrete slabs, water-dilutable coatings, open compacted soil, permeable synthetic surfaces, lattice stones, seepage pavers, drainage stones, high-performance infiltration pavers, sandy areas, gravel, dirt or crushed stone or pebble parking lots. Semi-permeable and permeable wastelands fall into this category.	

Category	Biodiversity hosting capacity coefficient	Description / Conditions	Calculation rule
Mixed surfaces	0.2	Air- and water-permeable materials allowing vegetation growth: grass pavers, grass gravel, wooden paving with wide joints, grass-jointed paving, grass grids, turf pavers.	
Impermeable mineral surfaces with trees	0.1	See previous descriptions	For these land cover types to be validated, tree density must exceed 2 individuals / 100 m ² . Otherwise, the area is considered "without trees".
Semi-permeable and permeable mineral surfaces with trees	0.2		
Mixed surfaces with trees	0.3		

8.2.3. Green spaces

Category	Biodiversity hosting capacity coefficient	Description / Conditions	Calculation rule	
Green spaces on slab	< 30 cm	Single plant stratum: herbaceous or shrubs	0.3*	Herbaceous: non-woody plants with generally short life cycles (grasses, clovers, asters, etc.). green space. Shrubs: woody plants < 7 m high (lavender, rosemary, honeysuckle, hornbeam, sage, hawthorn, etc.). Trees: woody plants > 7 m high (maples, linden, plane trees, chestnuts, pagoda trees, etc.). Examples: rooftop garden, vegetable garden on slab, in planters or pots. For the "shrub" layer to be effective, it must cover at least 20% of the green space. For the "tree" layer to be effective, it must cover at least 20% of the green space.
		Combination of 2 strata: herbaceous + shrubs	0.4	
	31–80 cm	Single plant stratum: herbaceous or shrubs or trees	0.4	
		Combination of 2 strata: herbaceous + shrubs, shrubs + trees, or herbaceous + trees	0.5	
		Combination of 3 strata: herbaceous + shrubs + trees	0.7	
	> 81 cm	Single plant stratum: herbaceous or shrubs or trees	0.5	
		Combination of 2 strata: herbaceous + shrubs, shrubs + trees, or herbaceous + trees	0.6	
		Combination of 3 strata: herbaceous + shrubs + trees	0.8	
	Open ground green spaces	Single plant stratum: herbaceous or shrubs or trees	0.7*	
Combination of 2 strata: herbaceous + shrubs, herbaceous + trees, shrubs + trees		0.8		
Combination of 3 strata: herbaceous + shrubs + trees		0.9		

Category	Biodiversity hosting capacity coefficient	Description / Conditions	Calculation rule
		networks (cables, pipes, etc.) do not preclude open ground status. • Made mainly of earthy materials: pedological/geological origin, fine granulometry (< 2 mm), sometimes low coarse fraction. For open ground green spaces with only a tree stratum (with gravel-covered soil for instance), refer to mineral or mixed surfaces with trees. Examples: wooded area, natural wasteland (free development for decades), urban parks, vacant lots, vegetable garden in open soil.	

8.2.4. Natural and agricultural spaces

Category	Biodiversity hosting capacity coefficient	Description
Large-scale monoculture	0.6*	Monospecific field (wheat, maize, etc.), may correspond to intensive farming systems
Meadow and pasture	0.7	Agricultural land (herbaceous vegetation) used for livestock feed
Temporary grassland	0.8	Poly-specific cultivation area (forage crops such as grasses and legumes) established for a limited period (often < 5 years). May correspond to extensive farming systems
Agricultural fallow < 5 years	0.7	Agricultural land abandonment < 5 years: habitat with herbaceous plants and shrubs (brambles)
Agricultural fallow > 5 years	0.8	Agricultural land abandonment > 5 years: habitat mainly composed of woody vegetation
Permanent grassland	0.9	Herbaceous area persisting for long periods (often decades), little or no tillage, without livestock presence
Natural areas	1	Natural area with minimal human impact: forests, meadows, dunes, wetlands, preserved woodlands, etc.

8.2.5. Wetlands

Category	Biodiversity hosting capacity coefficient	Description / Conditions
Basins and reservoirs	0.2*	Highly artificial water surface: fountain, reflecting pool, fire water basin, etc.
Impermeable wetlands	0.7	Natural or semi-natural water surface, with or without vegetation, permanent or temporary, with impermeable lining preventing water infiltration (liners, concrete...): ponds, retention basins, etc.
Permeable wetlands	1	Natural or semi-natural water surface, with or without vegetation, permanent or temporary, allowing infiltration into soil: ponds, swales, rain gardens, etc.
Infiltration swales	0.7	Channels often located along roads to collect runoff water, often dry
Ditches	0.8	Channels often located along roads to collect runoff water, often water-filled

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